

MATILDE

Migration Impact Assessment to Enhance
Integration and Local Development in
European Rural and Mountain Regions

Multi-dimensional policy recommendation matrix

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Deliverable 6.4 – Multi-dimensional policy-recommendation matrix

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Summary

The report D6.4 Multi-dimensional policy-recommendation matrix shows the interrelation between social, economic, integration and regional development policies. The implementation of the matrix and the collection of results from each MATILDE partner was coordinated by CUAS.

The policy recommendations consider different fields of action, all government levels from local to EU level and different groups of TCNs and are based on a mixed-methods approach. Thus, the qualitative and quantitative MATILDE results of WP3 and 4 as well as the results of participatory action research of WP5 were included.

Furthermore, as a final step in WP6, at least one policy roundtable was organised by each research partner. There, the pre-validated policy recommendations were jointly drafted, supplemented, adapted and validated. These were then transferred to the matrix and show recommendations and solutions on three levels of interconnectedness (government levels, areas of integration and groups of migrants).

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Introduction

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Background and Aim

The multi-dimensional policy recommendations and solutions matrix is imbedded in the WP 6 of the MATILDE project, that focuses on the “development of policy recommendations at strategic and operational level to improve the governance of migration” (MATILDE Grant Agreement No. 870831, 2019, 119). The aim of the multi-dimensional policy recommendations and solutions matrix is to highlight “the inter-relationship of social, economic integration-specific and regional development policies” (MATILDE Grant Agreement No. 870831, 2019, 119). The policy recommendations will consider different areas of action based on the mid-level theory of Ager & Strang (2008; adapted by Weidinger et al. 2017; further extended by Gruber et. al. 2020), all governmental levels from local to EU level and different groups of TCNs.

Of course, the focus of the individual MATILDE case study regions has differed, e.g. on the labour shortage in agricultural production, on the social inclusion of asylum seekers and refugees or on the implementation of language acquisition at local level. Following, the elaboration process of the challenges and policy recommendations was not done inevitably in every area of integration. Hence, they are concentrated in particular on the specific case study focus. Besides, the general focus was on the MATILDE objectives of social and economic impact of TCNs and local development. Nevertheless and due to the inter-relations, which will be explained below, there is a link to the other areas of integration. However, the named challenges and policy recommendations in the individual countries does not claim to be exhaustive. The recommendations mentioned, which were

developed and/or validated with the stakeholders during the policy roundtables and are now included in this report, also reflect the result of the practitioners' view and which priorities and urgencies they see.

Methodology

The policy recommendation and solutions matrix of each MATILDE country bases on a mixed-method approach. Following, the MATILDE results of the WP 3 and WP 4 were mainly conducted with the help of qualitative interviews as well as focus groups (qualitative research) and with quantitative analyses of descriptive and interpretative statistics (quantitative research). Additionally, the results of WP 5 were conducted within participatory action research in 13 case study regions in cooperation with the MATILDE local partners, aiming to involve important local and regional stakeholders (see Stakeholder Involvement Plan; Gruber et. al. 2020). Therefore, participatory research tools of the MATILDE toolbox were used and adapted to the local needs of each case study region, in order to engage a variety of stakeholders to participatory assess the role of TCNs in rural and mountainous regions in Europe (Membretti & Gilli 2022). This variety of stakeholders is displayed in the MATILDE quadruple helix model including political and public authorities, civil society, academia and research as well as businesses (Carayannis & Campbell 2009; see: Gruber et. al. 2020). Thus, the project results built on an involvement of stakeholders at all stages of participation in the sense of “Arnstein’s ladder of citizen participation” (Arnstein 1969), which was adapted to the stages of involvement within the MATILDE project from information over interactive involvement to joint creation (Gruber et. al. 2020). Especially, the last step of the elaboration of policy recommendations mainly based on a joint creation, due to the organisation of at least one policy roundtable in the frame of WP 6 by each research partner. There, the pre-validated policy recommendations, building on a SWOT-analysis (strengths, weaknesses, chances and threats) at all governance levels of the aforementioned results of the WP 3, 4 and 5 as well as scientific literature and further consultation of local and regional

stakeholders, were jointly co-designed, complemented, adapted and validated and hence, refer to the time of validation. When certain topics are mentioned in the policy recommendations, it does not mean, that there are no political measures and approaches in this context at all, but that further effort is recommended here. Additionally and in case of knowledge thereof, practical solutions were introduced. They show already existing practical examples which are working well and respond to a special challenge or need. Such practical solutions could be of interest for the implementation of the policy recommendations and for other governance levels, types of migration or MATILDE countries, considering that they are transferable. In order to offer a standard structure for the elaboration of policy recommendations, a guideline and i. a. templates for a SWOT-analysis and the matrix were provided.

In this phase, the inter-relation of social, economic integration-specific and regional development policies became more evident. In addition, inter-relations of those policies among the different governance levels appeared, which refers to the model of multi-level governance. “As the word, “multilevel” suggests, the concept of MLG [Multilevel Governance] comprises numerous state and non-state actors located at different levels, such as the local (sub-national), the national and the global (supranational).” (Saito-Jensen 2015, p. 2; see also: Gruber 2020) The need for a multi-level governance is explained i. a. by the distribution of competences among different political levels. This approach is aiming an improved cooperation and coordination of these levels. Especially, the competencies in migration and integration policies are distributed at all governance levels with contrary trends – the European Union has increasingly competences in migration policies, while integration policies made a “local turn” instead (Scholten & Penninx 2016; see also: Gruber 2020; Gruber & Zupan 2021). Besides, different groups of migrants are affected different by the migration and integration policies. For example, labour market integration might be restricted for asylum seekers, but not for recognised refugees.

Consequently, the policy recommendations and solutions matrix shows three levels of interconnectedness: 1) the inter-relations between governance levels/policies and areas of integration, 2) the inter-relations between areas of integration and types of migration, and 3) the inter-relations between governance levels/policies and types of migration.

Purpose

Migration and integration processes have a social, economic and territorial impact on the regions and vice versa. The governance processes in this frame are interdependent and have an influence on each other (Gruber 2020). Consequently, the policy recommendation matrix of each MATILDE country will evident the dispersal and interdependence of migration and integration policies over the different governance levels from local to the European Union and over different types of migration. In difference to a written report, the matrix tables help to display better at a glance the thematic and governance focus of each MATILDE country as well as the imbedded interdependences. The following policy recommendation matrixes will present the previously discussed inter-relationships of social, economic integration-specific and regional development policies within different areas of integration (Ager & Strang, 2008), various types of migration and interconnected at all governance levels.

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Austria

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In Austria, the case studies were conducted in Carinthia and Vorarlberg. In Vorarlberg, the local structures and processes of social integration of asylum seekers and refugees were analysed in three rural municipalities (Machold et. al. 2022). In Carinthia, the main objective was on the arrival and integration processes of old and new (female) refugees, with a special emphasis on the differences to high-skilled migrants, in the City of Villach and its rural surrounding (Gruber et. al. 2022).

Due to the research in both case study areas, policy recommendations for almost all areas of integration at local, regional, national and European level were formulated. The examples below display this interdependence in the matrix. For example, at both local levels, the lack of contacts between migrants in general and asylum seekers in particular with the local population is seen as problematic and different recommendations aim to increase the contacts. Nevertheless, these recommendations are interdependent with other areas of integration (e.g. “rights and citizenship” in Carinthia and “rural development” in Vorarlberg). This problem of lacking contacts including the respective recommendations is displayed from local to national level. Other recommendations are directed at EU level, for example, to introduce a monitoring system for the quality of accommodation and the care for asylum seekers in the integration area of “housing”, which is interlinked with the area of integration “rights and citizenship” at the same governance level. Consequently, the national and regional level need to set minimum qualification standards for refugee home operators and the caring staff as well as for the selection of the location of asylum shelters for quality assurance. For further insights in the policy recommendations and solutions to meet the main challenges in the Austrian case study region refer to the multi-dimensional policy recommendation matrix below.

1. Government level: local

Areas of integration	
Economy & Employment	Housing
In general:	In general:
<p>Carinthia (C): vacancies in the city centre</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> >increase visibility of migrant businesses >enable the use of vacant spaces for association meetings, etc. <p>C: labour shortage (e.g. in care, tourism, Infineon); V: vacancies particularly in health care, tourism, building industries</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> >qualify and integrate migrants for different professions. <p>C and V: Insufficient recognition of qualifications by employer</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> >support of the recognition processes >measures for the further qualification of migrants. 	<p>C: Restrictions on the allocation of public housing to TCNs</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> >Remove restrictions on the allocation of public housing <p>C: Desire of migrants to live in a central location (e.g. due to limited public transport)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> >Initiate expansion of public transport neighbourhood assistance (introduction to customs, welcome, information on waste separation, etc.) <p>C: Reservations of locals and migrants' lack of knowledge of customs and practices</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> >Initiate neighbourhood help (introduction to customs, welcome, information on waste separation, etc.) >Neighbourhood meetings to break down reservations >Create meeting spaces ("Werkraum", VOBIS) >Social housing projects ("intergenerational living"). <p>Vorarlberg (V): Private rental housing market is expensive</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> >all persons in need including refugees can register in social housing application list at the municipality, however waiting time is mostly long and criteria for application has long

	dependent on the duration of living and working in a certain municipality (not primarily on indigence).
Asylum seekers:	Asylum seekers:
V: Little job opportunities for (young) asylum seekers >re-install former neighbourhood aid (temporary employment, which is based on a direct contact between asylum seekers and locals) or >foster current "integration activities" by municipalities >facilitate the opportunity for an apprenticeship for young asylum seekers, which was forbidden between 2019-2021 and is now only possible after a rigorous labour market review.	
Refugees:	Refugees:
V: Structural discrimination in the job search >Help with job mediation and placement from volunteers - if there is trust and anchoring, this is very successful.	
Solutions:	Solutions:
C: Limited labour market access for asylum seekers >information about and use of service cheques. V: facilitate rigorous labour market review.	C: TAXES: Securing building land + linking subsidies to conditions + community spaces. V: since 2015 a housing allocation guideline of the federal state regulates access to social housing in a more objective and mandatory system of points.

Areas of integration	
Education	Health
In general:	In general:
<p>C: lack of child care/kindergarten places</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> >creation of sufficient kindergarten places >expansion of afternoon care >flexible offers: longer opening hours, flexible pick-up times, staggered price. <p>C: use schools & kindergarten as encounter zone for parents.</p> <p>V: Corona has brought disadvantage for people with migration background (digitization)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> >enormous engagement of teachers to mitigate these effects of corona >high participation of pupils in summer schools (advertised by coordinators of refugee care). <p>V: Danger of segregation in German classes.</p>	No information added.

Areas of integration		
Social connection/cohesion	Language & culture	Safety & stability
In general:	In general:	In general:
<p>C: Lack of contact between migrants and local population</p> <p>Prejudices, egoism</p> <p>How does a newcomer find a connection?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> >Involvement of migrant associations in city events (markets, trend sports days, Villach Church Day) 	<p>C: provision of multilingual information by the public administration (see: Rights & Citizenship).</p> <p>C: involvement of asylum seekers in translations of information materials/as first</p>	

<p>>Create premises for associations</p> <p>>Making successful examples of integration and intercultural encounters visible (e.g. in the city/community newspaper, on social media, at events).</p> <p>>Provide "possibility spaces" for joint activities (low-threshold, affordable rent, storage facilities, no compulsion to consume).</p> <p>C: Volunteering is associated with requirements and hurdles:</p> <p>>Improve information on associations, social organisations and volunteering.</p> <p>>Assumption of membership fees for certain groups of people (e.g.: at risk of poverty and exclusion)</p> <p>>Teaching the German language together with specialised knowledge</p> <p>>Recognition for voluntary work/volunteering.</p> <p>V: Three main approaches for social integration in a municipality</p> <p>>associations: each municipality has a number of different associations</p> <p>>voluntary work (group offers or individual accompaniment)</p> <p>>communal offers</p> <p>V: Lack of cooperation between standard system and volunteers</p>	<p>language peer counsellors (see Rights & Citizenship).</p> <p>C: evaluation of the language competencies of staff of public administrations (see Rights & Citizenship).</p>	
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<p>›multiplier and mediator at local level (e.g. mayor who is particularly important for community awareness) needed to negotiate with regional actors (NGOs like Caritas, etc.)</p> <p>V: Danger of overstrain and disappointment by volunteers</p> <p>›volunteers need support and counselling</p> <p>›clarification of responsibilities between different actors</p> <p>›contact person in municipality for integration issues.</p>		
<p>Asylum seekers:</p>	<p>Asylum seekers:</p>	<p>Asylum seekers:</p>
<p>C: enable contacts, integration and participation in events in Villach (s. Rights & Citizenship)</p> <p>V: enable contacts, integration and participation in numerous activities of volunteers and the municipality</p> <p>›former neighbourhood aid and now integration activities of the municipality.</p> <p>›group offers with regard to sports, language learning, cultural offers, etc. on voluntary basis</p> <p>›individual accompaniment is crucial in many stages of the asylum process</p> <p>›instalment of learning cafes, sewing cafes particularly important to reach women.</p>	<p>V: Many German learning activities by local volunteers, in the beginning course-like formats (with the lack of official courses in 2015 and 2016), afterwards focus on individual accompaniment.</p>	<p>V: Prejudices are stirred up by one-sided media reporting, uncertainties arise</p> <p>›Making refugees visible in the village, opportunities to get to know each other, reducing prejudices.</p>
<p>Refugees:</p>	<p>Refugees:</p>	<p>Refugees:</p>
<p>V: Potential of clubs for refugees not yet used (with the exception of sports clubs)</p>	<p>V: Many German learning activities by local volunteers, in the beginning course-like formats (with the lack of official courses in</p>	

<p>>refugees need a "bridge person" to overcome the barrier of the first entrance</p> <p>>low-threshold opportunities to participate</p> <p>>contact person in the municipality for the engagement on associations</p> <p>>on the other hand: high interest of refugee to participate in "blue light organization" because of creditability for citizenship - but often language problems.</p>	<p>2015 and 2016), afterwards focus on individual accompaniment.</p>	
<p>Solutions:</p>	<p>Solutions:</p>	<p>Solutions:</p>
<p>C: Lack of contact between migrants and the local population:</p> <p>>Implementation of integration guides, everyday help (mentors, buddies).</p> <p>C: Recognition of voluntary work, fundraising for associations -->Event.</p> <p>C: Campaign for positive coexistence in Villach, projects to promote intermixing, mutual understanding.</p> <p>V: Issues of integration as a permanent task for municipalities (not only in times of enhanced immigration)</p> <p>>instalment of a long-term contact person responsible for integration</p> <p>>Maintain regional coordinators for refugee care to support smaller municipalities.</p>	<p>C: establishment of specialised interpreting services/multilingual emergency call centres (see safety & stability; rights & citizenship).</p> <p>V: establishment of local meeting places where German is trained in an informal environment (accompaniment to official courses and possibility of language training): learning cafés, sewing cafés, talking cafés, low-threshold German courses, etc.; particularly important for women.</p>	<p>C: establishment of specialised interpreting services/multilingual emergency call centres (see Rights & Citizenship; Language and Culture).</p>

Areas of integration	
Mobility	Rights & Citizenship
In general:	In general:
<p>C: Inadequate public transport services (supply to the city districts, Sunday trips, connection to rural communities).</p> <p>Migrants often do not have a driving licence, work without public transport?</p> <p>>Increase public transport services (frequency, connection to ÖBB, connection to rural areas)-Improve transport connections to asylum centres</p> <p>>Renovate housing + enable public transport connections in rural areas</p> <p>>Expand cycle path infrastructure + easy access (language).</p> <p>C: Limited affordability of mobility</p> <p>>Financial support for certain groups of people (e.g. people at risk of poverty and exclusion, asylum seekers).</p> <p>C: Care places incl. housing + accessibility-How do migrants get to (public) contact points?</p> <p>>Mobility in connection with housing --> distribution/sharing-adaptation of the public transport structure (apps, language diversity etc.).</p>	<p>C: awareness raising for diversity, intersectionality and different social groups among administrative staff (e.g. in academy of public administration).</p> <p>C: involvement of NGOs to increase understanding of civil societies issues > understand NGOs as cooperation partners.</p> <p>C: promotion of intercultural/diversity-oriented & intersectional learning through...</p> <p>>use of existing institutionalisation of integration policy (integration department)</p> <p>>knowledge transfer from the integration department to others and vice versa</p> <p>>learning together: what are current issues/problems/specialities?</p> <p>C: provision of multilingual information by the public administration (see: Rights & Citizenship).</p> <p>C: involvement of asylum seekers in translations of information materials/as first language peer counsellors (see Rights & Citizenship).</p> <p>C: evaluation of the language competencies of staff of public administrations (see Rights & Citizenship).</p>

Asylum seekers:	Asylum seekers:
	C: enable contacts, integration and participation in events in Villach (s. Social Connection/Cohesion).
Refugees:	Refugees:
	C: information package after being granted asylum about housing, labour market, etc.
Solutions:	Solutions:
	C: strengthening of networking between politics, public administration, civil society and "affected persons": exchange meetings between the province of Carinthia, the city of Villach, NGOs, civil society, etc. C: establishment of specialised interpreting services/multilingual emergency call centres (s. Safety & Stability; Language & Culture).

Areas of integration
Rural/regional development
In general:
No information added.
Social connection/cohesion:
V: Crucial importance of social connections for all areas of integration, particularly in rural areas V: Social contacts are important that recognised refugees consider staying in rural areas. V: recognised refugee who stay in the rural municipality provide added value for the community, i.e. doing voluntary work in the municipality.

Mobility:

Migrants want to live in a central location (partly because of limited public transport - see also Mobility).

>Initiate neighbourhood assistance (introduction to customs, welcome, information on waste separation, etc.).

Inadequate public transport services (supply of the city districts, Sunday trips, connection to surrounding rural communities)

Often migrants do not have a driving licence, work without public transport?

>Increase public transport services (frequency, connection to ÖBB, connection to rural areas)-Improve transport connections to asylum centres

>Renovate housing + enable public transport connections in rural areas

>Expand cycle path infrastructure + easy access (language)

2. Government level: regional

Areas of integration	
Economy & Employment	Housing
In general:	In general:
<p>C and V: labour shortage (e.g. in health care, tourism, Infineon) >qualify and integrate migrants for different professions (modular training offer). C: limited access to labour market, especially for Muslim women >promoting access, especially for Muslim women. C: insufficient recognition of qualifications by employer >support of the recognition processes >measures for the further qualification of migrants. Thinking ahead in economic development: not just betting everything on one company, also see the needs of other companies.</p>	<p>V: Private rental housing market is expensive. C: Legal unequal treatment (housing subsidies: citizens, EU/EEA citizens & recognised refugees) Private housing market: too expensive, discrimination, too high securities >Abolition of legal unequal treatment in housing subsidies and housing allowances (third-country nationals are mainly affected; limited usability of housing subsidies for private persons). >Central Carinthia Contact Point for Housing Seekers >Departments of Social Affairs + Housing should seek solutions for individual cases.</p>
Asylum seekers:	Asylum seekers:
<p>C: exploit access to labour market for asylum seekers through employment in community jobs, cooperation with companies/associations/NGOs (s. Social Connection/Cohesion; Rights & Citizenship).</p>	<p>C: When choosing a location, pay attention to public transport connections and accessibility on foot to local amenities, authorities, playgrounds, etc. (see Rights & Citizenship).</p>

	<p>C: More social support through more staff in the neighbourhoods (+ better support key) (see Rights & Citizenship; Social Connection/Cohesion).</p> <p>C: Establish an "on-call contingent" with student internships and motivate community service workers (voluntary social year) and allow volunteers to help (e.g. cooking, doctor's appointments, shopping, hobbies, leisure activities...) (see Rights & Citizenship).</p> <p>C: Improve working conditions for caregivers (e.g. increase supervision for caregivers) (see Rights & Citizenship; Safety & Stability).</p> <p>C: Quality assurance: minimum qualification standards for neighbourhood workers and regular training (see Rights & Citizenship; Safety & Stability).</p> <p>V: 2015: agreement by all parties of the state parliament and the association of municipalities: asylum seekers accommodation in tents, containers or large-scale quarters should be avoided >accommodation in small-scale quarters in as many municipalities as possible.</p>
Refugees:	Refugees:
<p>V: insufficient recognition of qualifications by employer, particularly of higher educated women >support of the recognition processes >measures for further qualification of migrants.</p>	<p>V: After recognition of the asylum status and the granted right to stay, refugees drop out from basic care provision - strong housing needs >In many cases refugees were allowed to stay longer in basic care (but pay for it) as number of asylum seekers decreased</p>

<p>V: labour market integration of women less successful compared to men</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> >improve childcare provision also in rural areas >awareness building with regard to headscarves >question traditional role models. <p>V: Various projects aim to help refugees in search of employment, often no continuity and fragmented offers</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> >need for a continuous accompaniment by an integration coach (in transition phases between different courses and offers, but also between different institutions) >Programs needed where people can be permanently employed, both in the first and second labour markets. 	<p>>special housing program: "Wohnen 500" initiative developed by non-profit housing developers of Vorarlberg (VOGEWOSI). State subsidy is linked to the condition that one-third of the apartments are available for recognized refugees.</p>
<p>Solutions:</p>	<p>Solutions:</p>
<p>C: promotion of access, especially for Muslim women</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> >initiatives to raise awareness of employers (intercultural training). <p>C: measures for further qualification of migration</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> >expansion of A:LIFE project. <p>C: increase implementation of labour market integration projects, e.g. TourIK/A:Life (s. Rights & Citizenship; Social Connection);</p> <p>V: increase "integration activities" for asylum seekers (organized by Caritas) throughout all federal states.</p> <p>V: measure to enhance labour market participation for people with multiple (German) learning difficulties, e.g. "Work 1st".</p>	<p>V: >"Wohnen 500"</p> <p>>"secure renting" (Sicher vermieten): State of Vorarlberg offers landlords coverage for rent and operating arrears as well as for additional refurbishment costs to "combat" housing vacancies.</p>

V: competence check as fixed component of the labour market service in Vorarlberg: Projekt "CHECK IN" for all immigrants.

Areas of integration	
Education	Health
In general:	In general:
<p>C: lack of child care/kindergarten places</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> >creation of sufficient kindergarten places >creation of full-time places >expansion of afternoon care >flexible offers: longer opening hours, flexible pick-up times, staggered prices. <p>C: lack of coordination on migrants' potentials & knowledge gaps:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> >identify potentials and motivation of migrants and make them usable >educational offers for (young) migrants in line with the labour market's needs. <p>C: lack of support in school and training:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> >2-year support model to promote work and further training opportunities >information on training and further education opportunities in seminars of the integration agreement/in schools. 	<p>C: Mental health</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> >Increase mental health promotion offers >ESF = financial support also for health promotion >Crisis intervention team for war traumas -Health in connection with education (d. children) and work (jobs) >Strengthen self-competence-Women should receive financial support (stay longer with the children). <p>C: COVID-19 Impacts</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> >Appropriate response to COVID-19: physical and psychological impact on Carinthian population.

<p>C: information sheet on language assessment & German classes at school enrolment</p> <p>>more individual attention to the respective situation of the child</p> <p>>if possible, continuance in regular classes.</p>	
Refugees:	Refugees:
<p>Problem (P): Refugees' skills are often not recognised and they require to do new training.</p> <p>Recommendation (R): To recognise adequately these backgrounds and facilitate refugees' access to program to recognize officially their skills.</p>	

Areas of integration	
Social connection/cohesion	Language & culture
In general:	In general:
<p>C: Lack of contact between migrants & local population:</p> <p>>Information dissemination by local politicians about opportunities for intercultural encounter.</p> <p>>Making successful examples/projects of intercultural encounter visible.</p> <p>C: Volunteering with requirements and hurdles:</p> <p>>Assumption of membership fees for certain groups of people</p>	<p>C: evaluation of the language competencies of staff of public administrations (see Rights & Citizenship).</p>

>Teaching the German language together with specialist knowledge.
C: Lack of knowledge about important areas of life in Austria/Carinthia
>Education about education, health, labour market, housing, culture, values
>Emancipation: promotion of women - women's rights, equal rights, advice for men.
C: Reservations & negative attitude of politics and population towards migrants:
>Consideration of diverse groups in all political areas
>Sensitisation to intercultural settings
>Objectification of political discourses.
C: Political Agreement: Focus on strengths of immigration and migrants (see Rights & Citizenship).
C: Examination/monitoring of laws and regulations that have an exclusionary effect (see Rights / Citizenship).
C: Coming to terms with Carinthia's past on the topic of "foreignness" (see Rights & Citizenship)
C: Creating encounters and exchanges between the "old minority" and new immigrant population groups (see Rights & Citizenship).
V: Improve cooperation between local and regional level
>regional coordinator for refugee care.
V: Social integration, social cohesion has a different meaning and different impacts on males and females

<p>>acknowledge gender differences.</p> <p>V: Limited resources for municipal and regional offers with regard to social integration</p> <p>>Removing barriers to funding for full-time services and other initiatives.</p>	
Asylum seekers:	Asylum seekers:
<p>C: Lifting bans on entering (see Rights & Citizenship).</p> <p>C: Enable/encourage contacts, integration in and participation in events in Villach (see Rights & Citizenship).</p> <p>C: Utilise access to the labour market for asylum seekers through employment in municipal jobs, cooperation with companies/associations/NGOs, etc. (see Rights & Citizenship; economy & Employment).</p> <p>C: More social support through more staff in the neighbourhoods (+ better support ratio) (see Rights & Citizenship;).</p>	<p>C: increased offers of German language courses (more than 1h/week) incl. literary courses in small groups (s. Rights & Citizenship).</p> <p>C: accessibility of low-threshold German language courses for free outside asylum shelters (s. Rights & Citizenship).</p> <p>V: 2015-2017: high diversity of different funding possibilities and language course offers. 2018-2021: Shared responsibility of federal state and national level (ÖIF).</p>
Refugees:	Refugees:
	<p>V: 2015-2017: high diversity of different funding possibilities and language course offers. 2018-2021: Shared responsibility of federal state and national level (ÖIF).</p>
Solutions:	Solutions:
<p>C: Lack of contact between migrants and the local population:</p> <p>>Implementation of integration guides, everyday help (mentors, buddies).</p>	<p>V: 2015-2020: programme to support volunteers to give lectures in German "okay.zusammen lernen".</p>

<p>C: Lack of knowledge about important areas of life in Austria/Carinthia: >Welcome brochures incl. online information collection (multilingual, up-to-date, easy to access)</p> <p>C: Further development of refugee work into integration work (incl. arrival management): Development of guidelines/checklists for standardised information dissemination in municipalities (see Rights & Citizenship).</p> <p>C: Expansion of integration office - mediator from communities</p> <p>C: More projects like "Hera" - permanent! Increased implementation of</p> <p>C: Central Carinthian contact point for housing seekers, contact seekers...</p> <p>C: Labour market integration projects like TourIK or A:Life (see Rights & Citizenship; Economy & Employment).</p> <p>V: Regional coordinator of refugee care - permanent!</p> <p>V: Strengthen cooperation of associations and migrants organization</p> <p>V: Allocation of information and guidelines, such as "Ankommen in Vorarlberg".</p>	<p>V: Project "deutsch4alle": development for learning material for voluntary accompaniment of refugees in German learning.</p> <p>V: "Work 1st" project to support recognised refugees with low German knowledge to prepare for regional (first) labour market and improve knowledge of German language.</p>
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Areas of integration	
Safety & stability	Mobility
In general:	In general:
	<p>C: Inadequate public transport services (supply to the city districts, Sunday trips, connection to rural communities). Migrants often do not have a driving licence, work without public transport? >Increase public transport services (frequency, connection to ÖBB, connection to rural areas)-Improve transport connections to asylum centres >Renovate housing + enable public transport connections in rural areas >Expand cycle path infrastructure + easy access (language)</p> <p>C: Limited affordability of mobility >Financial support for certain groups of people (e.g. people at risk of poverty and exclusion, asylum seekers)</p> <p>C: Care places incl. housing + accessibility-How do migrants get to (public) contact points? >Mobility in connection with housing --> distribution/sharing-adaptation of the public transport structure (apps, language diversity etc.).</p>
Asylum seekers:	Asylum seekers:
C: improve working conditions for care workers (s. Housing) > quality assurance: minimum qualification standards for	

workers in shelters & regular training (s. Housing; Rights & Citizenship).	
Solutions:	Solutions:
	<p>C: Allocation/distribution of migrants (evenly + intercommunal Cooperation).</p> <p>C: Thinking utopias.</p>

Areas of integration	
Rights & Citizenship	Rural/regional development
In general:	In general:
<p>C: establish a coordinated integration management at all political levels between Federal State, districts & municipalities > evaluation of existing processes/allocation of resources.</p> <p>C: intercultural education for local/regional politicians > education of population.</p> <p>C: promotion of "place-based policies" through regional structures (incl. NGOs).</p> <p>C: involvement of NGOs to increase understanding of civil societies issues > understand NGOs as cooperation partners.</p> <p>C: promotion of intercultural/diversity-oriented & intersectional learning through...</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> >use of existing institutionalisation of integration policy (integration department) >knowledge transfer from the integration department to others and vice versa >learning together: what are current issues/problems/specialities? <p>C: evaluation of the language competences (s. Language & Culture).</p>	

<p>C: evaluation/monitoring of policies with an exclusionary effect (e.g. Minimum Income Act: enable training (s. Social Connection/Cohesion).</p> <p>C: political agreement: focus on strengths of migration & migrants (s. Social Connection/Cohesion).</p> <p>C: reflection of the Carinthia's past on "foreignness" (s. Social Connection/Cohesion).</p> <p>C: create meeting & exchange of "old" minority and new immigrant population groups (s. Social Connection/Cohesion) > promotion of a self-confident approach to one's own origins & roots (s. Social Connection/Cohesion).</p> <p>C: promotion of applied and participatory research on the topic of old and new minorities (s. Social Connection/Cohesion)</p>	
<p>Asylum seekers:</p>	
<p>C: choice of location of asylum shelters with public transport connection or walking distance to local amenities, authorities, playgrounds, etc. (s. Housing).</p> <p>C: adaption of entry bans (s. Social Connection/Cohesion).</p> <p>C: exploit access to labour market for asylum seekers (s. Employment; s. Social Connection/Cohesion) > implementation of EU Directive (2013/33/EU).</p> <p>C: increase social care: more staff in shelters (+ better care ratio) (s. Social Connection/Cohesion) > establish a "stand-by" contingent and allow volunteers to support (s. Housing)</p> <p>>medical care should always be guaranteed.</p> <p>C: improve working conditions for care workers > quality assurance: minimum qualification standards for workers in shelters & regular training (s. Housing; Safety & Stability).</p> <p>C: acceleration of asylum procedures.</p>	

<p>C: increased offers of German language courses (more than 1h/week) incl. literary courses in small groups (s. Language & Culture).</p> <p>C: accessibility of low-threshold German language courses for free outside asylum shelters (s. Language & Culture).</p>	
	<p>Mobility:</p>
	<p>C: Migrants want to live in a central location (partly because of limited public transport - see also Mobility).</p> <p>>Initiate neighbourhood assistance (introduction to customs, welcome, information on waste separation, etc.).</p> <p>C: Inadequate public transport services (supply of the city districts, Sunday trips, connection to rural surrounding communities)</p> <p>Often migrants do not have a driving licence, work without public transport?</p> <p>>Increase public transport services (frequency, connection to ÖBB, connection to rural areas)</p> <p>>Improve transport connections to asylum centres</p> <p>>Renovate housing + enable public transport connections in rural areas</p> <p>>Expand cycle path infrastructure + easy access (language).</p>

Solutions:	Solutions:
<p>C: improvement of coordination & governance of integration in the Federal State (interface for municipalities, districts, state and federation): application of regional managers or regional integration coordinators</p> <p>C: raising awareness of staff in public administration for diversity, intersectionality and different social groups: intercultural and diversity-sensitive trainings for public administration,</p> <p>C: strengthening of networking between politics, public administration, civil society, "affected persons": exchange meetings of Federal State of Carinthia, City of Villach, NGOs, civil society, etc.</p> <p>C: development of refugee work to integration work (incl. arrival management): development of guidelines/checklists for standardised information dissemination in municipalities (s. Social Connection/Cohesion)</p> <p>C: increased implementation of labour market integration projects, e.g. TourIK & A:Life (s. Economy & Employment;; Social Connection).</p>	

3. Government level: national

Areas of integration	
Economy & Employment	Housing
In general:	In general:
<p>Labour shortage</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> >recognition of qualifications (one-stop-shop) >facilitate access to the labour market and access to trainings for migrants >future perspective: identify jobs of the future, of the regions - match with training opportunities & potentials on the labour market (training background) >increase attractiveness of system-relevant jobs (care, health, energy, childcare). <p>Legal restrictions on the recognition of qualifications</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> >facilitate recognition processes >lower barriers to recognition of qualifications. <p>COVID-19 measures</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> >strengthening regionality. <p>Match labour market needs with training opportunities for TCNs for further qualification (s. Rights & Citizenship).</p>	<p>Rental housing market is expensive</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> >building of social housing and cooperative apartments to cover price increase. <p>Non-equal access to housing market - discrimination of people with migrant backgrounds / forced migrants</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> >objective allocation criteria. <p>Non-equal distribution of migrants and non-migrants in social housing - danger of segregation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> >settlement management.

Asylum seekers:	Asylum seekers:
<p>Re-introduction of the integration year for all asylum seekers (s. Rights & Citizenship).</p> <p>utilise the potential of asylum seekers & training (qualification) in areas with a need of employees (e.g. make resources available through language training & further education) (s. Rights & Citizenship)</p> <p>>specific educational offers for different qualifications.</p> <p>Consideration of the needs of society as a whole, not only control by the economy.</p>	<p>Have a say in the distribution of refugees and the location of neighbourhoods (see Rights & Citizenship).</p> <p>When choosing locations, pay attention to public transport connections and accessibility on foot to local amenities, authorities, playgrounds, etc. (see Rights & Citizenship).</p> <p>More social support through more staff in the neighbourhoods (+ better support ratio) (see Rights & Citizenship).</p> <p>Establish a "stand-by contingent" with student internships and motivate civilian servants (voluntary social year) and allow volunteers to provide support (e.g. cooking, doctor's appointments, shopping, hobbies, leisure activities, learning German...) (see Rights & Citizenship; Social Connection/Cohesion; Language & Culture).</p> <p>Improve working conditions for caregivers (e.g. increased supervision offers for caregivers) (see Rights & Citizenship)</p> <p>Quality assurance: minimum qualification standards for neighbourhood workers & regular training (see Rights & Citizenship)".</p>
Refugees:	Refugees:
<p>Re-introduction of the integration year to promote labour market integration & social integration (s. Rights & Citizenship).</p>	

Labour migrants:	Labour migrants:
<p>Labour shortage & Red-White-Red Card</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> >facilitate access to the Red-White-Red Card for highly-qualified migrants >realistic salary requirements (s. Rights & Citizenship). 	

Areas of integration	
Education	Health
In general:	In general:
<p>Lack of child care/kindergarten places</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> >guaranteed kindergarten places for all children >2nd year of mandatory kindergarten attendance (for certain target groups - not sure about this restriction) >expansion of afternoon care. <p>Lack of coordination on migrants' potentials & knowledge gaps:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> >consider needs of regional labour market >link training & employment. <p>Lack of support at school & in training:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> >strengthening school social work & psychology >expansion of mother-tongue teaching with more mother-tongue teachers >raise awareness of teachers for intercultural teaching/learning 	<p>Low educational and income levels of migrants as well as low health competence decrease self-awareness of health (ÖIF-Forschungsbericht: Migration in Österreich: Gesundheitliche und ökonomische Aspekte).</p>

<p>›recognize multilingualism as competence. inclusive classes (comprehensive school) (s. Rights & Citizenship) versus "German Support Classes". Non-equal distribution of "Brennpunktschulen" in rural and urban areas ›Enhanced support for "Brennpunktschulen" (https://www.vienna.at/pilotprojekt-zur-unterstuetzung-von-brennpunktschulen-startet-im-herbst/6928527).</p>	
<p>Asylum seekers:</p>	<p>Asylum seekers:</p>
	<p>Health care is often difficult because of limited knowledge of German and low health competence and education ›Promoting social work accompaniment in health care (raising awareness of mental illness, translations, etc.). ›Raising awareness among health workers about cultural differences.</p>
<p>Unaccompanied minor refugees (UMRs):</p>	<p>Unaccompanied minor refugees (UMRs):</p>
	<p>COVID-19 has caused many mental health problems: Increase in lethargy, dejection and loss of perspective in adolescents. ›Promote Mobile Youth Work (address consequences of Covid-19).</p>
<p>Solutions:</p>	<p>Solutions:</p>
<p>Mitigate disadvantages (because of corona) for children (particularly experienced by children non-German mother tongues): "summer school".</p>	

Areas of integration	
Social connection/cohesion	Language & culture
In general:	In general:
<p>Lack of contact between migrants and local population: >Change in the understanding of integration - according to the EU definition "a dynamic, two-way process of mutual accommodation by all immigrants and residents of EU Member States".</p> <p>Reservations and negative attitudes of politicians and the local population towards migrants: >Objectification of political and media discourses (>Consideration of diverse groups in all policy areas: hier Gefahr der "Abstempelung bestimmter Bevölkerungsgruppen, wie zB die Muslime, würde ich weglassen!).</p> <p>Promotion of place-based policies through regional structures (incl. NGOs) (see Rights & Citizenship).</p> <p>Facilitate political participation and access to citizenship (examine Bauböck citizenship model) (see Rights & Citizenship).</p> <p>TCNs: Alignment of conditions for permanent residence with EU citizens (see Social Connection/Cohesion) (see Rights & Citizenship).</p> <p>Political Agreement: Focus on potentials and strengths of immigration and migrants (see Rights & Citizenship).</p>	<p>C: evaluation of the language competencies of staff of public administrations (see Rights & Citizenship).</p>
Asylum seekers:	Asylum seekers:

<p>Establish a "stand-by contingent" with student internships and motivate civilian servants (voluntary social year) and allow volunteers to provide support (e.g. cooking, doctor's appointments, shopping, hobbies, leisure activities, learning German...) (see Rights & Citizenship; Housing; Language & Culture).</p>	<p>Facilitate participation in e.g. language courses by offering child care, group-specific courses, good accessibility of services.</p> <p>Establish a "stand-by" contingent with student internships, civilian servants (voluntary social year) & volunteers to provide support (e.g. cooking, doctor's appointments, shopping, hobbies, leisure activities, learning German, ...) (s. Rights & Citizenship; Housing; Social Connection/Cohesion). Increased offers of German language courses (more than 1h/week) incl. literary courses in small groups (s. Language & Culture).</p> <p>Attendance of official language classes (starting with B2) is costly.</p>
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Areas of integration	
Safety & stability	Mobility
In general:	In general:
No information added.	No information added.

Areas of integration	
Rights & Citizenship	Rural/regional development
In general:	In general:
<p>Promotion of "place-based policies" through regional structures (incl. NGOs) (s. Social Connection & Cohesion).</p> <p>Inclusive classes (comprehensive school) (s. Language & Culture).</p> <p>Match labour market needs with training opportunities for TCNs for further qualification (s. Economy & Employment).</p> <p>Facilitate political participation & access to citizenship (evaluate citizenship model acc. Bauböck) (s. Social Connection/Cohesion).</p> <p>Align conditions for permanent residence with EU citizens (s. Social Connection/Cohesion).</p> <p>Representation: diversity (migration, people with disabilities, gender, sexual orientation, youth, elderly, etc.) of the population should be reflected in chambers & other representative bodies (e.g. municipal councils).</p> <p>Political agreement: focus on the strengths of immigration & migrants (s. Social Connection/Cohesion).</p>	
Asylum seekers:	
<p>Distribution of asylum seekers & the location/management of asylum shelters</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> >Co-determination by Federal States >choice of location with public transport connection or walking distance to local amenities, authorities, playgrounds, etc. (s. Housing) >increase social care: more staff in shelters (+ better care ratio) (s. Social Connection/Cohesion) > establish a "stand-by" contingent and allow volunteers to support (s. Housing) 	

<p>›improve working conditions for care workers › quality assurance: minimum qualification standards for workers in shelters & regular training (s. Housing; Safety & Stability). Acceleration of asylum procedures & increase of transparency - increase number of employees in the Federal Office for Immigration and Asylum (BFA) ›use country report to reduce the need of re-opening of asylum procedures in order to prevent retraumatisation & to increase efficiency of procedures ›enable opportunities for permanent residence (save costs & increase integration efforts). Increased offers of German language courses (more than 1h/week) incl. literary courses in small groups (s. Language & Culture). Re-introduction of the integration year for all asylum seekers (s. Economy & Employment) ›utilise the potential of asylum seekers & training in areas with a need of employees (s. economy & employment). Promotion of NGOs: better use of regional know-how of NGOs & regional infrastructure.</p>	
<p>Refugees:</p>	
<p>Re-introduction of the integration year to promote labour market integration & social integration (s. economy & employment).</p>	
<p>Labour migrants:</p>	
<p>Labour shortage & Red-White-Red Card ›facilitate access to the Red-White-Red Card for highly-qualified migrants ›realistic salary requirements (s. economy & employment).</p>	
	<p>Mobility:</p>
	<p>Rural areas mostly rely on private transportation. Limited mobility for people dependant on public transportation</p>

>Improve reliable public transportation in rural areas.

4. Government level: European

Areas of integration			
Economy & Employment	Housing	Education	Health
In general:	In general:	In general:	In general:
<p>Create legal channels to enter EU, especially in connection with labour migration (simplify visa policies) (s. Rights & Citizenship).</p> <p>Expand & uniform implementation of the Blue Card Directive (2009/50/EC; conditions of entry and residence of third-country nationals for the purposes of highly qualified employment)</p> <p>>Reduce entry requirements (s. Rights & Citizenship).</p>	<p>No uniform minimum requirements for the reception/provision/integration of migrants</p> <p>>Extend the competences of the EU</p> <p>>Define minimum standards for reception, care, integration.</p> <p>No uniform minimum requirements in accommodation/provision of housing</p> <p>>Extend EU competences</p> <p>>Define minimum standards for accommodation/housing allocation.</p>	<p>No information added.</p>	<p>No uniform minimum requirements for health care</p> <p>>Extend EU competences</p> <p>>Define minimum standards for health care.</p>

Asylum seekers:	Asylum seekers:	Asylum seekers:	Asylum seekers:
	EU-wide regulations on accommodation and care in initial reception centres and mandatory compliance with existing regulations + fines for non-compliance (see Rights & Citizenship).		

Areas of integration		
Social connection/cohesion	Language & culture	Safety & stability
In general:	In general:	In general:
No information added.	No information added.	
Asylum seekers:	Asylum seekers:	Asylum seekers:
		<p>Enabling "safe flight": protection of people during flight (s. Rights & Citizenship)</p> <p>Create legal channels to enter EU, especially with regard to resettlement initiatives.</p> <p>>coordination of EU activities (Gerald Knaus "Welche Grenzen brauchen wir").</p> <p>Stop pushbacks at external borders (s. Rights & Citizenship).</p> <p>Prevent trafficking in human beings (s. Rights & Citizenship).</p>

		<p>FRONTEX should not only secure borders but also ensure orderly and safe arrivals (e.g. safe sea crossings) (instead of defence) (s. Rights & Citizenship).</p> <p>Visa vs. flight: legal & safe flight (protection mandate before asylum application) (s. Rights & Citizenship).</p>
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Areas of integration		
Mobility	Rights & Citizenship	Rural/regional development
In general:	In general:	In general:
No information added.	<p>Expand EU competence in integration policies</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> >create EU-wide minimum standards in labour market, housing, social integration, etc. in the MS. >create legal channels to enter EU, especially in connection with labour migration (s. Economy & Employment). <p>Expand & uniform implementation of the Blue Card Directive (2009/50/EC; conditions of entry and residence of third-country nationals for the purposes of highly qualified employment)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> >Reduce entry requirements (s. Economy & Employment). <p>Provide low-threshold information on funding for NGOs & institutions; simplify administrative procedures. Simplify administrative procedures (s. Regional Development).</p> <p>Increase available budget for research & knowledge transfer between organisations.</p>	<p>Provide low-threshold information on funding for NGOs & institutions; simplify administrative procedures. Simplify administrative procedures (s. Rights & Citizenship).</p>

Asylum seekers:	Asylum seekers:	
	<p>Relieve burden on MS at the external borders by introducing a quota system: 1.5% of the country's population as asylum seekers (reasonable limit + fine for non-compliance).</p> <p>Making the distribution of asylum seekers in MS visible (transparency barometer).</p> <p>Standardised asylum procedures in the EU.</p> <p>Continually revise EU-wide list of safe countries.</p> <p>Align the rights of beneficiaries of subsidiary protection with those of recognised refugees in the MS.</p> <p>EU-wide regulation on accommodation & care in initial reception centres + fines for non-compliance (see Housing).</p> <p>Monitoring system: quality of accommodation & care, reporting (see Housing).</p> <p>Enabling "safe flight": protection of people during flight (s. Safety & Stability).</p> <p>Stop pushbacks at external borders (s. Safety & Stability).</p> <p>Prevent trafficking in human beings (s. Safety & Stability).</p> <p>FRONTEX should not only secure borders but also ensure orderly and safe arrivals (e.g. safe sea crossings) (instead of defence) (s. Safety & Stability).</p> <p>Visa vs. flight: legal & safe flight (protection mandate before asylum application) (s. Safety & Stability).</p>	

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Bulgaria

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In Bulgaria, the policy recommendations were developed under the guiding topic “Local development and innovative practices on migration, mobility, integration and inclusion”, which was the title of the policy roundtable, too. The inherent multilevel governance and multidimensionality of topics within the areas of integration were considered, consequently. In addition, good practices and practical solutions were focused (Koleva & Ninova 2022). With reference to MIPEX (Solano & Huddleston 2020), Bulgaria’s main policy problems occur in the following areas of integration: economy and employment, education, social connection/cohesion, language and culture as well as mobility. These challenges also refer to the case study on “impact on community-space interactions, territorialisation and sense of belonging of rural/mountainous localities through TCN integration” (Koleva 2021, 68). The multidimensional policy recommendations and solutions matrix evidently present the inter-relationship of social, economic and territorial integration policies in Bulgaria. For example, it is recommended at local level in the area of education, to provide additional language programs in Bulgarian language for TCNs and TCN children, which is interdependent with the area of language and culture and is additionally mentioned at the regional governance level. Furthermore, it includes a practical solution. Also, the need of cooperation in various settings is mentioned in different areas of integration (rural development, economy and employment, education, social connection) and at different governance levels, which proves the inherent interdependency of this recommendation. For further insights in the policy recommendations and solutions to meet the main challenges in the Bulgarian case study region refer to the multi-dimensional policy recommendation matrix below.

1. Government level: local

Areas of integration			
Economy & Employment	Housing	Education	Health
In general:	In general:	In general:	In general:
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Working groups with active TCNs to discuss strategies for attracting tourists and long-term migrants; - Free consulting services for TCNs provided by local administration regarding the purchase of property in the region - Free consulting for TCNs on various administrative services + business consulting for entrepreneurs. 	No information added.	Systematically meet the need of TCNs to acquire Bulgarian language skills: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Plan additional funding to meet the need for Bulgarian language classes for TCN children in school - Provide additional Bulgarian language programs for TCNs and TCNs children in schools - Support TCNs wanting to engage in volunteering and social action. 	No information added.
Solutions:	Solutions:	Solutions:	Solutions:
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Many TCNs have successfully developed business initiatives in the region or small businesses such as restaurants and beauty salons, barbershops etc. 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Two English migrants have started a school for teaching and coaching in English oriented towards adults, children and teams in the town of Harmanli. - An innovative form of school 'Playschool' created in 2014 by two British migrants teaches children refugee children in the Registration 	

		and reception Center (RRC) Harmanli through play work.	
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Areas of integration		
Social connection/cohesion	Language & culture	Safety & stability
In general:	In general:	In general:
<p>Need to enhance social connections between locals and TCNS:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Organise, disseminate and communicate common intercultural events; - Regular information about municipal intercultural events should be published on the website in Bulgarian and English (See Language&Culture) - Provision of logistical and financial support from the municipality for the conduction of initiatives - Provision of opportunities for networking. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Support foreign nationals living in the region willing to engage in volunteering and social action (for example provision of English lessons); - Publish regularly on the website of Haskovo District in Bulgarian and English a schedule of intercultural events related to art, music, sport and ecology in the villages in the region; - Provide all administrative documents in English to the foreign citizens living in Haskovo District (See Rights&Citizenship); - Provide additional Bulgarian language programs for TCNs and TCNs children in schools in the Haskovo and Harmanli region (See Education). 	No information added.
Solutions:	Solutions:	Solutions:
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The region has a very positive experience with intercultural artistic or green events and there are members of the migrant community who are willing to organize events such as 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - There are many examples of TCNs in the region of Haskovo and Harmanli who are engaged in volunteering aimed at improving community life. 	

<p>international art festivals.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - In the region there are numerous TCNs with an active lifestyle and business or with ideas and projects for the promotion of the region who are already successfully promoting the region through their network with the different opportunities it provides. 		
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Areas of integration		
Mobility	Rights & Citizenship	Rural/regional development
In general:	In general:	In general:
<p>Enhance local mobility:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Improvement and renovation of the transport network; - Provision more and more regularly inter-village bus lines in Haskovo District. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Provision of all basic administrative documents to be accessible in English. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Establish institutionally a cooperation between active migrants to promote the region as a tourist destination and a place for long-term migration. - Create programs and conditions that enable active migrants to promote the region as ‘Ambassadors of Tourism’.
Solutions:	Solutions:	Solutions:
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The paperwork for residency that is filled in the relevant institution in Haskovo is already available also in English following several complaints in relation to this issue. 	<p>Many TCNs with an active lifestyle and business are successfully promoting the region through their network.</p>

2. Government level: regional

Areas of integration			
Economy & Employment	Housing	Education	Health
In general:	In general:	In general:	In general:
- Establish institutionally a cooperation between active migrants who in their role as 'Ambassadors of Tourism in Haskovo Region' to help to promote the region as a tourist destination but also as a place for long-term migration.	No information added.	- Provision of additional Bulgarian language programs for TCNs and TCNs children in schools in the Haskovo and Harmanli region.	No information added.
Solutions:	Solutions:	Solutions:	Solutions:
- In the region there are numerous TCNs with an active lifestyle and business or with ideas and projects for the promotion of the region who are already successfully promoting the region through their network with the different opportunities it provides.			

Areas of integration		
Social connection/cohesion	Language & culture	Safety & stability
In general:	In general:	In general:
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Support foreign nationals living in the region willing to engage in volunteering and social action (for example provision of English lessons); - Publish information about upcoming events on the website of Haskovo District in Bulgarian and English. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Support foreign nationals living in the region willing to engage in volunteering and social action (for example provision of English lessons); - Published regularly on the website of Haskovo District in Bulgarian and English a schedule of intercultural events related to art, music, sport and ecology in the villages in the region; provide all basic administrative documents in English to foreign citizens living in Haskovo District; - Provide additional Bulgarian language programs for TCNs and TCNs children in schools in the Haskovo and Harmanli region. 	No information added.
Solutions:	Solutions:	Solutions:
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Two English migrants have started a school for teaching and coaching in English oriented towards adults, children and teams in the town of Harmanli. - An innovative form of school 'Playschool' created in 2014 by two British migrants teaches children refugee children in the Registration and reception Center (RRC) Harmanli through play work. - The region has a very positive experience with intercultural artistic or green events and there are members of the 	

	migrant community who are willing to organize events such as international art festivals.	
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Areas of integration		
Mobility	Rights & Citizenship	Rural/regional development
In general:	In general:	In general:
Enhance regional mobility - Improvement and renovation of the transport network; - Provision more and more regularly inter-village bus lines in Haskovo District.	- Provision of all basic administrative documents to be accessible in English for foreign citizens living in Haskovo District.	Establish institutionally a cooperation between active migrants to promote the region as a tourist destination and a place for long-term migration. - Create programs and conditions that enable active migrants to promote the region as ‘Ambassadors of Tourism’.
Solutions:	Solutions:	Solutions:
	- The paperwork for residency that is filled in the relevant institution in Haskovo is already available also in English following several complaints in relation to this issue.	- In the region there are numerous TCNs with an active lifestyle and business or with ideas and projects for the promotion of the region who are already successfully promoting the region through their network with the different opportunities it provides.

3. Government level: national

Areas of integration			
Economy & Employment	Housing	Education	Health
In general:	In general:	In general:	In general:
- Creation of a strategy to attract foreign workers and retrain them according to the needs of the economy of specific regions and sectors.	- Improvement of the infrastructure of the refugee camp by adding a functioning space for art activities.	- Provision of additional Bulgarian language programs for TCNs and TCNs children in schools in the Haskovo and Harmanli region.	No information added.
Solutions:	Solutions:	Solutions:	Solutions:
		The initiative Intercultural Gardens as Green Bridges organized by the Bulgarian MATILDE team in schools in Harmanli and Haskovo region proved to be a successful good practice that connects children from different countries and cultures in an innovative way	

Areas of integration		
Social connection/cohesion	Language & culture	Safety & stability
In general:	In general:	In general:
- Sustainable cooperation between state authorities and the NGO sector to train educators and psychologists. (See Education).	No information added.	No information added.
Solutions:	Solutions:	Solutions:
The initiative Intercultural Gardens as Green Bridges organized by the Bulgarian MATILDE team in schools in Harmanli and Haskovo region proved to be a successful good practice that connects children from different countries and cultures in an innovative way.		

Areas of integration		
Mobility	Rights & Citizenship	Rural/regional development
In general:	In general:	In general:
No information added.	No information added.	- Strategy to attract foreign workers and retrain them according to the needs of the economy of specific regions and sectors.

4. Government level: European

Areas of integration			
Economy & Employment	Housing	Education	Health
In general:	In general:	In general:	In general:
No information added.	No information added.	No information added.	No information added.

Areas of integration		
Social connection/cohesion	Language & culture	Safety & stability
In general:	In general:	In general:
No information added.	No information added.	No information added.

Areas of integration		
Mobility	Rights & Citizenship	Rural/regional development
In general:	In general:	In general:
No information added.	No information added.	TCNs with successful businesses initiatives and TCNs demonstrating strong entrepreneur potential to be identified and invite to national and European coaching

		seminars, business forums, job fairs and intercultural workshops to share their best practices.
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Finland

Authors: Lauri Havukainen, Pirjo Pöllänen, Daniel Rauhut, Magnus Enlund

The case study in Ostrobothnia discussed strategies to prevent the outmigration of TCNs, in order to meet the labour shortage in the region, while the case study in North Karelia examined the meaning of languages (Rauhut & Enlund 2022; Davydova-Minguet et. al. 2022). Following, the challenges focus on language acquisition, labour market integration and the need of an increased cooperation of important stakeholders. To meet these challenges, the policy recommendations and solutions in the multi-dimensional matrix mainly refer to the appropriate areas of integration. The interdependence of the areas of integration is – for example – noticeable in the policy recommendations to economy and employment at regional level, where increased education and language learning is recommended, in order to overcome labour-intensive jobs. Improvements in the Finnish language – on the other hand – influence the integration in local associations, which is a policy recommendation for language and culture at local level. In addition, the policy recommendation about on-the-job training, mentioned for education at national level, has an impact on the labour market integration at local level and influences the development of the labour market in the region. Hence, these aspects also need to be considered at different governance levels. For further insights in the policy recommendations and solutions to meet the main challenges in the Finnish case study regions refer to the multi-dimensional policy recommendation matrix below.

1. Government level: local

Areas of integration			
Economy & Employment	Housing	Education	Health
In general:	In general:	In general:	In general:
No information added.	No information added.	The public authorities often promote Finnish as the language of integration (e.g. in integration courses) even in Swedish speaking areas of the country. This can contradict the Finnish constitution and hinder chances of local integration. - MIGRI should be guided to enforce the current legislation which already gives Swedish equal status as a language of integration. This should be done regionally with the local language in mind.	No information added.

Areas of integration		
Social connection/cohesion	Language & culture	Safety & stability
In general:	In general:	In general:
Sports clubs and other leisure time activity organizers are still in a bystander role in integration even though their activities attract immigrants and could easily attract more.	The lingua franca language within a multicultural association can exclude people	No information added.

<p>Particularly in rural surroundings where the number of possible activities is often limited.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - While some hobbies such as football and music already play a significant role in integration of immigrant children, more emphasis should still be placed on them. <p>Municipalities, multicultural NGOs and working groups should integrate clubs better. Activity of the clubs should also be promoted and educated.</p> <p>Organization of integration activities is not always clear between the public and third sector and project base funding of NGOs causes instability.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Establish working groups with all the relevant actors with lead of the municipality. Municipalities have more continuity and stability not effected as much by funding and staff changes. 	<p>from activities and hinder integration if it is not the local language.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Promote the use of local language as the language used in the NGOs as it helps with integration and establishing relations with the community. 	
<p>Solutions:</p>	<p>Solutions:</p>	<p>Solutions:</p>
<p>Larger cities like Joensuu in North Karelia already has a municipal wide multicultural working group with wide variety of societal actors participating. This, however, is rare in more rural municipalities. At least in Lieksa, North Karelia we managed to get two important actors on the same table to discuss co-operation. We also would have liked get the municipality involved in their potential partnership.</p>		

Areas of integration		
Mobility	Rights & Citizenship	Rural/regional development
In general:	In general:	In general:
No information added.	No information added.	No information added.

2. Government level: regional

Areas of integration			
Economy & Employment	Housing	Education	Health
In general:	In general:	In general:	In general:
<p>In rural areas in both regions the labour market is mostly low-productive and labour intensive. Heavy reliance on low-productive, labour intensive and often low paid work will slow down the structural change of the economy in the region and lead to underdevelopment.</p> <p>- A diversification of the economic structure is needed, and in such diversification, immigrants can play a vital role. Investments from all government levels are needed.</p>	<p>Many rural areas suffer from lack of proper housing. This causes car decency as available housing is often in more remote places in rural areas.</p> <p>- While investments in housing and public transport might not be economically feasible in long term they still should be looked into.</p>	No information added.	No information added.

Asylum seekers:	Asylum seekers:	Asylum seekers:	Asylum seekers:
<p>While labour intensive jobs are a good stepping stone for asylum seekers, this can also stagnate individuals socioeconomic progress in long term.</p> <p>- Investments in language education and education in general will help asylum seekers and refugees advance socioeconomically.</p>	<p>If asylum seekers and refugees are settled in remote areas of rural municipalities, they may struggle with everyday life as many do not have a car or a licence and the public transport is meagre at best.</p> <p>- Asylum seekers should be placed in areas where access to services and job opportunities are reachable without a car.</p>		
Refugees:	Refugees:	Refugees:	Refugees:
<p>While labour intensive jobs are a good stepping stone for refugees, this can also stagnate individuals socioeconomic progress in long term.</p> <p>- Investments in language education and education in general will help asylum seekers and refugees advance socioeconomically.</p>	<p>If asylum seekers and refugees are settled in remote areas of rural municipalities, they may struggle with everyday life as many do not have a car or a licence and the public transport is meagre at best.</p> <p>- Refugees should be placed in areas where access to services and job opportunities are reachable without a car.</p>		

Labour migrants:	Labour migrants:	Labour migrants:	Labour migrants:
Many jobs attracting labour migrants are seasonal in nature and do not provide means for more permanent residence, even if there is will towards it. This especially in agriculture heavy Ostrobothnia. - Making residence permits more flexible and diversification of the economy will help establish more permanent residence.			
Solutions:	Solutions:	Solutions:	Solutions:
	When the current Ukrainian refugee situation started it seems that something has been learned from past mistakes as many of the new reception centres have been placed in population centres.		

Areas of integration		
Social connection/cohesion	Language & culture	Safety & stability
In general:	In general:	In general:
Local multicultural associations, other NGOs and public institutions interregional communication and co-operation is often lacking. This can hinder small actors' possibilities, especially when the best practices or applying funding or organizing activities are not known.	No information added.	No information added.

- Local multicultural associations, other NGOs and public institutions should co-operate and co-ordinate activities, strategies and practices better regionally. Applying for funding is one major issue this could help with. Regional working groups and networks need to be promoted and established.		
Solutions:	Solutions:	Solutions:
We managed to organize at least some sort of meetings that include actors from Lieksa, Kitee and JoMoni, the multicultural association of Joensuu region.		

Areas of integration		
Mobility	Rights & Citizenship	Rural/regional development
In general:	In general:	In general:
	No information added.	No information added.
Labour migrants:	Labour migrants:	
North Karelia and Ostrobothnia are not well known internationally and this causes issues when attracting labor migrants. Both regions have advantages that are poorly promoted. - The regions need to do more and better place marketing and place branding.		

Solutions:	Solutions:	Solutions:
Both North Karelia and Ostrobothnia have educational institutions that have been successful in student recruitment from abroad. Now we just need structures to make them stay after graduating.		

3. Government level: national

Areas of integration			
Economy & Employment	Housing	Education	Health
In general:	In general:	In general:	In general:
- Creation of a strategy to attract foreign workers and retrain them according to the needs of the economy of specific regions and sectors.	No information added.	The new curriculum for the integration education is directing language learning and language teaching towards on-the-job learning. However, this is a demanding task for rural areas as there often are not enough on-the-job training position in the private job market. Also, the competitive tendering done every few years hinders the education organizers chances of developing their programs. Tendering also favours private businesses over the often more experienced and qualified local educational institutions. - There should be nationwide instructions for municipalities for offering and organizing these on-the-job learning positions for immigrants and quotas for immigrants in the public sector organisations for their on-the-job learning positions. The suppliers of language courses	No information added.

		should be guaranteed better continuity to develop their language teaching and the role and practices of tendering changed.	
Labour migrants:	Labour migrants:	Labour migrants:	Labour migrants:
Many jobs attracting labour migrants are seasonal in nature and do not provide means for more permanent residence, even if there is will towards it. This especially in agriculture heavy Ostrobothnia. - Making residence permits more flexible and diversification of the economy will help establish more permanent residence.			
Solutions:	Solutions:	Solutions:	Solutions:
		According our knowledge a lot to guarantee better continuity for the integration courses can already be achieved with the current legislation. It up to the political will of the politicians and public officials to actually make it reality.	

Areas of integration		
Social connection/cohesion	Language & culture	Safety & stability
In general:	In general:	In general:
No information added.	No information added.	No information added.

Areas of integration		
Mobility	Rights & Citizenship	Rural/regional development
In general:	In general:	In general:
No information added	<p>The line demarking between what responsibilities society has for its new residents and what obligations the new residents have in the integration process is often vague and blurry. Both politicians and practitioners as well as immigrants have an incomplete perception on rights, obligations, responsibilities, and duties.</p> <p>- It should be clarified what kind of help, how much and for how long society will give. Parallel to this, what the new residents are expected to do should also be clarified. Here the new act on integration could and hopefully can bring change.</p>	No information added
Labour migrants:	Labour migrants:	
	<p>Some groups like the elderly and labour immigrants are often dropped out from language learning and integration courses as they are focused for unemployed immigrants and refugees.</p> <p>- There should be national guidelines and economic support for local actors on how to substitute the language learning of those migrants who are not involved in the</p>	

	integration courses. More on-the-job integrated language learning. This issue is hopefully addressed in the new integration legislation.	
Family migrants:	Family migrants:	
	<p>Some groups like the elderly and labour immigrants are often dropped out from language learning and integration courses as they are focused for unemployed immigrants and refugees.</p> <p>- There should be national guidelines and economic support for local actors on how to substitute the language learning of those migrants who are not involved in the integration courses. More on-the-job integrated language learning. This issue is hopefully addressed in the new integration legislation.</p>	
Other:	Other:	
	<p>Some groups like the elderly and labour immigrants are often dropped out from language learning and integration courses as they are focused for unemployed immigrants and refugees.</p> <p>- There should be national guidelines and economic support for local actors on how to substitute the language learning of those migrants who are not involved in the integration courses. More on-the-job integrated language learning. This issue is hopefully addressed in the new integration legislation.</p>	
Solutions:	Solutions:	Solutions:
	The new curriculum for integration courses has more on-the-job learning integrated into it but as stated elsewhere this also raises issues, particularly in rural areas.	

4. Government level: European

Areas of integration			
Economy & Employment	Housing	Education	Health
In general:	In general:	In general:	In general:
No information added.	No information added.	No information added.	No information added.

Areas of integration		
Social connection/cohesion	Language & culture	Safety & stability
In general:	In general:	In general:
No information added.	No information added.	In local level the NGOs are not familiar enough with different possibilities to make effective use of EU funding. In many NGOs, project-based funding is causing problems setting up activities in the long run. - The EU funding instruments for local and regional actors, NGOs, should be more easily accessible and there should be better continuity for project-based activities. It should be considered how small but efficiently operating NGOs could create activities that have opportunity for more stable and permanent funding.

Areas of integration		
Mobility	Rights & Citizenship	Rural/regional development
In general:	In general:	In general:
No information added.	No information added.	No information added.

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Germany

Author: Tobias Weidinger

In Bavaria, the MATILDE case study region of Germany, the (health) care sector, the hospitality industry, and handicraft were put in context with the TCN employment in three rural districts (Kordel et al. 2021). Employment of TCNs is crucial (1) for the companies to pursue one's business despite of a shortage of workers, (2) for the regions to maintain a diversified regional economy, and (3) for the migrants to fulfil themselves and build up a future in the countryside (Kordel et al. 2022). Given the existing labour shortage, the aim should be to promote the recruiting and onboarding of TCN employees and support their well-being and retention (Weidinger et al. 2022). However, these processes are hindered by the inconsistency of policies through different interpretation and implementation of laws at the lower governance levels. With regard to the case study objective, the main challenges in economy and employment include bureaucracy, a lack of knowledge of employers and TCNs about their own rights, opportunities and responsibilities as well as negative attitudes toward TCNs among employers, colleagues and clients/patients. To address these challenges, the multi-dimensional matrix offers several policy recommendations. It is suggested, for instance, to foster intercultural opening at different governance levels (local and national), and to consider employers as important stakeholders in integration issues. This issue is also related to the area of integration for language and culture at local and for social connection/cohesion at local, regional, national and EU level. For more insights on policy recommendations and solutions to address key challenges in the German case study regions, please see the multi-dimensional policy recommendations matrix below.

1. Government level: local

Areas of integration			
Economy & Employment	Housing	Education	Health
In general:	In general:	In general:	In general:
Addressing employers as important actors of integration, fostering intercultural opening, apply target-group specific communication, establish external or in-house relocation management and regular meeting encounters, offer tandem and mentoring programmes, work-accompanying language courses, financial incentives, flexible work models and long holidays to VFR, qualification measures and support for qualification.	Found or nurture existing social housing associations and construct apartments, support by employers, local administration, welfare organizations, NGOs and refugee relief groups with regard to TCNs' access to private housing.	Safeguarding places in all-day child care and schooling infrastructures, better information of TCNs about child care offers and apprenticeship in Germany, training and qualification of nursery school teachers and school teachers, establish lending services for technical equipment, construction of nurseries and kindergartens.	Provision of therapeutical counselling services, consider health holistically and include both social and leisure aspects in municipal health concepts; strengthening interculturally sensitive communication of such concepts.

Areas of integration		
Social connection/cohesion	Language & culture	Safety & stability
In general:	In general:	In general:
Making presence of TCNs at and the diverse history of immigration in places more visible, fostering interaction between TCNs and the local resident population.	Prioritisation of acquisition of German language, offer different forms of communication and specific places to communicate, intercultural opening of local administration, nurseries, kindergartens, schools, general practitioners, hospitals, public transport companies, police, customs authorities and the justice system.	No information added

Areas of integration		
Mobility	Rights & Citizenship	Rural/regional development
In general:	In general:	In general:
Digitisation of bureaucratic procedures to prevent everyday mobility, improving everyday mobility by means of providing bicycles, lifts or shuttle busses, fostering public transport offers, reducing language barriers for on-demand offers and reimbursing costs for volunteers who provide lifts. To allow TCNs to pursue driving school and buy an own car, loans or (partial) reimbursements by the state or employers could be offered.	Transparent and clear responsibilities, welcoming receptions for TCNs and parties for naturalisation, rural citizenship documents, low-threshold opportunities for participation, establishment of integration advisory boards, opening up offers for all immigrants & refugees.	
Asylum seekers:	Asylum seekers:	
Prevention of everyday mobility by means of decentralised counselling.		
Refugees:	Refugees:	Social connection/cohesion:
Prevention of everyday mobility by means of decentralised counselling.		Strengthening regional networks and cooperation, gain support from local elites and key stakeholders

UMRs:	UMRs:	UMRs:
Prevention of everyday mobility by means of decentralised counselling.		
Family migrants:	Family migrants:	Rights & Citizenship:
		Welcome hubs as first contact points at the local administration, merging existing (parallel) structures in village development, economic development and integration work.

2. Government level: regional

Areas of integration			
Economy & Employment	Housing	Education	Health
In general:	In general:	In general:	In general:
Support small and medium-sized enterprises with regard to recruiting, better communicate opportunities for the recognition of foreign credentials and provide loans, deferrals of payments and (partial) waivers for the recognition process.		Hire additional staff for nurseries, kindergarten and school, extend curriculum of prospective teachers, strengthen programmes for exam companions.	No information added.
Asylum seekers:	Asylum seekers:	Asylum seekers:	Asylum seekers:
	Apply algorithm-based matching processes to allocate asylum seekers, asylum accommodation should be equipped with internet and Wi-Fi.		

Refugees:	Refugees:	Refugees:	Refugees:
	Apply algorithm-based matching processes to allocate resettlement refugees- Refugees should be placed in areas where access to services and job opportunities are reachable without a car.		
UMRs:	UMRs:	UMRs:	UMRs:
	Apply algorithm-based matching processes to allocate UMRs.		

Areas of integration		
Social connection/cohesion	Language & culture	Safety & stability
In general:	In general:	In general:
Maintain and consolidate prevention programmes addressing racism and intercultural opening of society.	Maintain and consolidate programmes for lay cultural and language interpreting.	No information added.

Areas of integration		
Mobility	Rights & Citizenship	Rural/regional development
In general:	In general:	In general:
No information added.	Transparent and clear responsibilities, definition of integration as mandatory task, replacement of a target group orientation in offers with a group orientation.	
Refugees:	Refugees:	Health:
		Social connection/cohesion: regular formats of exchange between local stakeholders about the topic of immigration and integration.
Mobility:	Mobility:	Mobility:
		Rights & Citizenship: provide funding consultants and a 'local integration package'.

3. Government level: national

Areas of integration			
Economy & Employment	Housing	Education	Health
In general:	In general:	In general:	In general:
Expand capacities at the customs authorities, implement mandatory time recording in hospitality industry, support the intercultural opening of the workforce, provide counselling offers with regard to information about qualification and education of (TCN) newcomers as well as self-employment, better communicate opportunities for the recognition of foreign credentials, evaluation of the Temporary Employment Act.	Construction of social housing.	Evaluate minimum requirements for the provision of language & integration courses.	Provision of psychological and therapeutical offers for TCNs, safeguard support in terms of substance counselling.

Asylum seekers:	Asylum seekers:	Asylum seekers:	Asylum seekers:
Evaluation of the temporary work permits for asylum seekers.			
Refugees:	Refugees:	Refugees:	Refugees:
		Evaluate the residence rule for recognised refugees.	

Areas of integration		
Social connection/cohesion	Language & culture	Safety & stability
In general:	In general:	In general:
Maintain and consolidate federal programmes for intercultural opening of society and fostering democracy.	Provide more opportunities to learn the language, initiate image campaigns about the advantages of multilingualism.	No information added.

Areas of integration		
Mobility	Rights & Citizenship	Rural/regional development
In general:	In general:	In general:
Check, if recognition of foreign driving licenses is possible without prior tests, re-fund travel costs to language and integration courses in an easy way.	Transparent and clear responsibilities, definition of integration as mandatory task, replacement of a target group orientation in offers with a group	

	orientation, hire more staff for the visa departments of the embassies and the Federal Office for Migration and Refugees, foster family reunification, provide TCNs with a right to vote at least on the local level, exploit the potential for naturalisation of TCNs.	
Family reunion:	Family reunion:	Rights & Citizenship:
		Provide enough funding for the purpose of integration, including emergency funds.

4. Government level: European

Areas of integration			
Economy & Employment	Housing	Education	Health
In general:	In general:	In general:	In general:
No information added.	Maintain and consolidate funding for the intercultural opening of the workforce and facilitate the recognition of professional qualifications.	Define internet connection and Wi-Fi as minimum requirements for asylum accommodation.	No information added.

Areas of integration		
Social connection/cohesion	Language & culture	Safety & stability
In general:	In general:	In general:
Maintain and consolidate programmes for intercultural opening of society	No information added.	No information added.

Areas of integration		
Mobility	Rights & Citizenship	Rural/regional development
In general:	In general:	In general:
No information added.	Replacement of a target group orientation in offers with a group orientation.	
		Rights & Citizenship:
		Dismantle bureaucratic hurdles for small cities and rural districts and municipalities in rural and mountain areas with regard to applications for EU funding, better use ERDF funds for the topic of integration.

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Italy

Author: Mia Scotti

The Italian case studies were geographically and thematically divided. In South Tyrol, the case study objective was the labour market integration of TCNs, while in the Metropolitan City of Turin, the focus was on the territorial and social impact of TCNs settlement in a mountainous region (Gilli & Membretti 2022). Hence, the results build on a variety of different aspects in the TCNs inclusion in rural regions, which were discussed and policy recommendations elaborated – due to its complexity – in two roundtables (Scotti 2022). Nevertheless, the main problems arose in the frame of the following areas of integration: economy and employment, rights and citizenship, education, health, mobility, and housing. For example, the migration policies do not meet the economic needs in Italy. In consequence, it is explained in the policy recommendations and solutions matrix at a national level to increase the access and to change policies towards welcoming for different groups of TCNs. Such changes would also meet the challenge, located at local level in “rights and citizenship”, of a lack of work permissions. Consequently, challenges and policy recommendations are linked in various areas of integration and have an impact at different governance levels. For further insights in the policy recommendations and solutions to meet the main challenges in the Italian case study region refer to the multi-dimensional policy recommendation matrix below.

1. Government level: local

Areas of integration			
Economy & Employment	Housing	Education	Health
In general:	In general:	In general:	In general:
	<p>Challenges:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Lack of housing facilities; - High costs of housing; - Mistrust of local owners to rent to TCNs; - poor housing conditions <p>Possible solutions /recommendations:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Public support in the form of payment guarantee; - Rehabilitation of abandoned or underused buildings in inland/ mountainous areas - Co-housing approach and hostels for temporary inhabitants. 	<p>Challenges:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - High NEET rates across TCNs; - Lower education higher among TCNs in respect to Italians. <p>Possible solutions /recommendations:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Flexible integrative training, formative activities, afternoon and evening didactic activities, workshops, activities connected with local traditions and vocations, psychological support for scholars and families. 	<p>Challenges:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Low offer and access to public health services; difficulties in receiving health services do to cultural, language and religious barriers; <p>Possible solutions /recommendations:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Proximity services; cultural mediators, target actions. Roundtables suggestion: cultural mediators for both TCNs and local communities.

Labour migrants:	Labour migrants:	Labour migrants:	Labour migrants:
<p>Challenges:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - labour market is marked by high seasonality; intense/ Demand for just some months; - TCNs employed in less socially desirable jobs; <p>Possible solutions/ recommendations:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Professional training, accredited training, check of competences, life-long learning, peer-to-peer training, cultural mediation activities and projects. 			
Solutions:	Solutions:	Solutions:	Solutions:
<p>MARKAS (private company implementing equity management policies and actions). - engagement in workspace atmosphere surveys; - staff training & talent; - support creative solutions for TCNs workers to overcome the language problem; check of competencies implementation.</p>	<p>Home for 1 euro: Some small Italian municipalities sell started 'houses for 1 euro' with the possibility of buying houses for 1 euro by settling in the territory; Domus Sportello: Projects to support people housing and job opportunities access through awareness initiatives.</p>		

Areas of integration		
Social connection/cohesion	Language & culture	Safety & stability
In general:	In general:	In general:
<p>Challenges: a peaceful but separate coexistence among TCNs and locals; fears and mistrust of local communities.</p> <p>Possible solutions/ recommendations: mutual exchange and cooperation between locals and new arrivals; local initiatives with a multi-level approach (the one which involves various local actors); actions and projects with specific and concrete objectives centred on the exchange (e.g., offering training to migrants and involving them in initiatives relevant to the community such as the maintenance of land and forests or the promotion of rural commons initiatives;</p> <p>Roundtables suggestion: relocate fears in public space debate.</p>	<p>Challenges: a multilingual context increases integration difficulties.</p> <p>Possible solutions/ recommendations: language training and target projects to improve language learning</p>	

Asylum seekers:	Asylum seekers:	Asylum seekers:
Challenges: migrants not interested in staying permanently on the territory.		Challenges: irregularly crossing of the alps with risks to their physical safety.
Refugees:	Refugees:	Refugees:
Challenges: migrants not interested in staying permanently on the territory.		
Family migrants:	Family migrants:	Family migrants:
Challenges: Migrants women more excluded from social life due to family's duties.		
Other:	Other:	Other:
		Local historical fragmentation does not help migrants, who struggles to find a place.
Solutions:	Solutions:	Solutions:
Building workshop as done in ST, physically building something for the community and TCNs favouring inclusion and exchange (Camposaz project).	Morus onlus projects: Moro Onlus activated a of Coro Moro (a choral activity) to help TCNs learn Italian while approaching traditional local songs.	FIRST aid stations and rescue service (MigrAlp project).

Areas of integration		
Mobility	Rights & Citizenship	Rural/regional development
In general:	In general:	In general:
Challenges: low frequency and poor capillarity of public transport particularly elderly, migrants, students and women; TCNs have less frequently a private car. Possible solutions/recommendations: Improve flexible transport and community-managed services such as carpooling or social taxis may represent a solution to this problem guaranteeing benefits for all.		No information added.
Labour migrants:	Labour migrants:	Labour migrants:
	Challenges: not enough work permission availability in respect to labour supply and demand= out of quota migration phenomenon which turn in to irregular situations.	
Solutions:	Solutions:	Solutions:
"TAXI SOCIALE". Small municipalities in Italy activated a social taxi, a public shared taxi service that can be rented to access basic services (hospitals/schools) locally.		

2. Government level: regional

Areas of integration			
Economy & Employment	Housing	Education	Health
In general:	In general:	In general:	In general:
No information added.	No information added.	<p>Challenges: low connection of formative offer with local tradition and needs; inefficient planning of school services at a regional level; low involvement of local stakeholders in regional planning; unsustainability of public services in low densely populated areas.</p> <p>Possible solutions/recommendations: Effective public service planning; local stakeholder involvement in service planning. When it comes to inclusion, schools play a crucial role.</p>	<p>Challenges: health service offers points far from small municipalities; low capillarity of the health services across territories; low involvement of local stakeholders in regional planning; unsustainability of public services in low densely populated areas.</p> <p>Possible solutions/ recommendations: innovative services: e.g. communities' nurse and midwife; telemedicine; local stakeholder involvement in service planning; Institutionalisation of experiences and best practices; Foster linkages between local realities and national decision makers.</p>

Solutions:	Solutions:	Solutions:	Solutions:
		Local, regional and national service planning roundtables - SNAI (Italy Inner area National strategy) experience.	Project CONSENSO. Community Nurse Supporting Elderly in a changing Society - activation of a nurse who visits the patients and not the opposite.

Areas of integration		
Social connection/cohesion	Language & culture	Safety & stability
In general:	In general:	In general:
Roundtables suggestion: Educational institutions should be more involved in the inclusion projects and debate; Welcoming and inclusion require time, resources and targeted investments.	No information added.	No information added.

Areas of integration		
Mobility	Rights & Citizenship	Rural/regional development
In general:	In general:	In general:
Challenges: low frequency and poor capillarity of public transport in rural and mountainous areas; economic unsustainability of public services in low densely populated areas; low involvement of local stakeholders in regional planning. Possible solutions/recommendations:	No information added.	

innovative services; Institutionalisation of experiences and best practices; Foster linkages between local realities and national decision makers.		
Other:	Other:	Other:
		<p>Migrant's interest in mountain and rural places seem low: in fact, not all of them see the mountains as a place where they can take root.</p> <p>Many migrants come from densely urban contexts in their countries of origin, and they seem used to a lifestyle that has little to do with the mountain and rural ones.</p>
Solutions:	Solutions:	Solutions:
Local, regional and national service planning roundtables - SNAI (Italy Inner area National strategy) experience.		

3. Government level: national

Areas of integration			
Economy & Employment	Housing	Education	Health
In general:	In general:	In general:	In general:
Challenges: approach to migration utilitarian and poorly based on a mutual benefits strategy Possible solutions/ recommendations: reverse the trend to structured policies to welcome TCNs Roundtables suggestion: Building a culture of exchange.	Challenges: not equal and adequate housing policies; low access to housing facilities Possible solutions/recommendations: reverse the trend to structured policies to welcome TCNs.	No information added.	No information added.
Labour migrants:	Labour migrants:	Labour migrants:	Labour migrants:
Challenges: Yearly entrance quote plans and temporary work permission visa underestimates/overestimates National labour market's needs; Irregular employment, few guarantees for the workers; underestimation of the contribution of migrant workers to the economic system; labour exploitation, low self-employment.	Challenges: Migrants often find work but not a home, especially in rural areas, and are forced into shanty towns or poor housing conditions.		

Possible solutions/recommendations: better target work visa permission; widening micro-credit opportunities and access; guidance and mentorship programme; Improve public opinion and political actors' knowledge of the contribution of foreign immigrants to the Italian economy and society.			
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Areas of integration		
Social connection/cohesion	Language & culture	Safety & stability
In general:	In general:	In general:
<p>Challenges: lack of governance; low stakeholders' involvement; abandonment of successful integration experiences (SPRAR); political instrumentalisation of the migration issue; fear and misinformation.</p> <p>Possible solutions/recommendations: National migration and Data policy; Enhancing migration impact assessment.</p> <p>Roundtables suggestion: Fears should not be isolated but rather be relocated in a national debate/ Everyone actor has to feel a sense of belonging to a process to make it his own.</p>	No information added.	

Asylum seekers:	Asylum seekers:	Asylum seekers:
Challenges: complex system of not unitary measures and actions.		Challenges: slowness of administrative and bureaucratic procedures; Policies, laws and rules changes.
Labour migrants:	Labour migrants:	Labour migrants:
		Challenges: slowness of administrative and bureaucratic procedures; Policies, laws and rules changes

Areas of integration		
Mobility	Rights & Citizenship	Rural/regional development
In general:	In general:	In general:
No information added.	Challenges: difficulty to obtain a regular migrant status = low rights = low participation in local social life.	Challenges: population decline and abandonment in rural and mountainous areas. Possible solutions/recommendations: The demographic theme and the issue of territorial inequalities must be put in relation with migration policies. Roundtables suggestion: In Italy's inland and mountainous areas there are several underestimated effectiveness opportunities in terms of inclusion of new inhabitants, including foreigners;/ To be effective, projects must take into account the territorial dimension of their application.

4. Government level: European

Areas of integration			
Economy & Employment	Housing	Education	Health
In general:	In general:	In general:	In general:
No information added.	No information added.	No information added.	No information added.

Areas of integration		
Social connection/cohesion	Language & culture	Safety & stability
In general:	In general:	In general:
No information added.	No information added.	No information added.

Areas of integration		
Mobility	Rights & Citizenship	Rural/regional development
In general:	In general:	In general:
No information added.	No information added.	No information added.

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Norway

Authors: Veronica Blumenthal, Maria Taivalsaari Røhnebæk, Deniz Akin and Signe-Lise Dahl

In Norway, two regions were selected for the case study research in the MATILDE project: Midt-Gudbrandsdal (MG) and Nord-Østerdal (NØ) in Innlandet county. During the participatory research in WP 5, concrete ideas for integration and inclusion were developed. These ideas centered around the following areas of integration: economy and employment, social connection, language and culture, mobility as well as rights and citizenship (Røhnebæk et. al. 2022). Although there are some measures aiming to improve some of these areas, there is a need for further effort to strengthen the economic and social integration of migrants. There is, for example, a high threshold for labour market participation among immigrants in the region. Consequently, the multi-dimensional policy recommendations and solutions matrix include, for example, the idea of structured recognition procedures for non-formal qualifications. Such a national-level initiative would have a strong impact on the labour market at the regional level, where lowering the barriers to labour market participation is recommended. For further insights into the policy recommendations and solutions to meet the main challenges in the Norwegian case study regions, please see the multi-dimensional policy recommendation matrix below.

1. Government level: local

Areas of integration			
Economy & Employment	Housing	Education	Health
In general:	In general:	In general:	In general:
No information added.	No information added.	No information added.	
Solutions:	Solutions:	Solutions:	Solutions:
			"Right activity for all". A scheme offering free leisure activities (activity passes) for underprivileged youth.

Areas of integration		
Social connection/cohesion	Language & culture	Safety & stability
In general:	In general:	In general:
To be socially active in inclusive and safe surroundings are key to immigrant integration at the local level. It is through these arenas that newcomers socialize and acquire particular skills that contribute to their employment and language acquisition, both important components of their integration to the society at large. Immigrants, however, face a number of barriers for social participation and inclusions that should be addressed.	See description under "social connection/cohesion" Policy recommendations: • Mentors: Door openers to language and social integration. Examples of different iterations of such mentor systems include:	No information added.

<p>Policy recommendations:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Making information on events and activities more accessible: Establish a local information sharing platform. • Activity passes & subsidized leisure activities for migrants and underprivileged youth. • Inclusion policies & initiatives directed at single household immigrants. • Enhance engagement of the volunteer sector as a supplement to the public refugee services. 	<p>“Language buddies”, Local guides, and Welcome coordinators:</p>	
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Areas of integration		
Mobility	Rights & Citizenship	Rural/regional development
In general:	In general:	In general:
No information added.	No information added.	No information added.

2. Government level: regional

Areas of integration			
Economy & Employment	Housing	Education	Health
In general:	In general:	In general:	In general:
<p>At the regional level, there is also a need for policies that will strengthen opportunities for immigrants' labour market participation, which will also benefit the regions' economic growth.</p> <p>Policy recommendations:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lowering the barriers to labour market participation: Establishing a "job central". • Improve migrant's mobility (see "Mobility"). • Improve access to vocational education opportunities for migrants in rural areas. • Entrepreneurial courses specifically adapted to immigrants. 	No information added.	No information added.	No information added.

Areas of integration		
Social connection/cohesion	Language & culture	Safety & stability
In general:	In general:	In general:
No information added.	No information added.	No information added.

Areas of integration		
Mobility	Rights & Citizenship	Rural/regional development
In general:	In general:	In general:
<p>There is a strong need for new initiatives that will enable geographic mobility in the case regions, as mobility is critical for social and labour market participation of the residents.</p> <p>Policy recommendations: Improve migrant's mobility by facilitating driver's license obtainment through: 1) Suppling theory classes (digitally) in different languages, in cooperation with other regions. 2) Facilitation of practical driving training in cooperation with the volunteer sector unsustainability of public services in low densely populated areas; low involvement of local stakeholders in regional planning.</p> <p>Possible solutions/recommendations: Innovative services; Institutionalisation of experiences and best practices; Foster linkages between local realities and national decision makers.</p>	No information added	No information added-

3. Government level: national

Areas of integration			
Economy & Employment	Housing	Education	Health
In general:	In general:	In general:	In general:
No information added.	No information added.	Strengthening opportunities for labour market inclusion by lowering the thresholds for acquiring and documenting formal qualifications. Policy recommendations: • Structured support and recognition procedures for non-formal qualifications.	No information added.
Solutions:	Solutions:	Solutions:	Solutions:
		Pilot: Module based education for adults. The essence of these pilots is that the training is divided into smaller training units (modules) which can be more flexibly combined with work experience which in the end can lead to a formal certificate of competence (trade certificate).	

Areas of integration		
Social connection/cohesion	Language & culture	Safety & stability
In general:	In general:	In general:
No information added.	No information added.	No information added.

Areas of integration		
Mobility	Rights & Citizenship	Rural/regional development
In general:	In general:	In general:
No information added.	No information added.	Enhance predictability and communication for local settlement and integration work. Policy recommendations: A more regional perspective and increased predictability in assignment of refugees to municipalities by 1) Rewarding municipalities/regions that successful in their resettlement, qualification and integration effort, by prioritizing these municipalities/regions when allocating refugees. And 2) the national government should emphasize inter-municipal/ regional cooperation when assigning refugees to municipalities and not just the individual municipalities.

4. Government level: European

Areas of integration			
Economy & Employment	Housing	Education	Health
In general:	In general:	In general:	In general:
No information added.	No information added.	No information added.	No information added.

Areas of integration		
Social connection/cohesion	Language & culture	Safety & stability
In general:	In general:	In general:
No information added.	No information added.	No information added.

Areas of integration		
Mobility	Rights & Citizenship	Rural/regional development
In general:	In general:	In general:
No information added.	No information added.	No information added.

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Spain

Authors: Raúl Lardiés-Bosque, Nuria del Olmo Vicén

The case study in Spain was conducted in the rural region of Aragón with the focus on the impact of foreign immigrants aiming a demographic and socioeconomic revitalisation of the region (Lardiés-Bosque & del Olmo Vicén 2022a). In this sense, one of the focus for the elaboration of policy recommendations was at the local level, even though decisions at regional and national level have an impact at local level; so, the need for a multi-level governance in terms of migration and integration became obvious, as it was especially seen during the roundtables. There, the participating stakeholders highlighted the limitation of their competencies (Lardiés-Bosque & del Olmo Vicén 2022b). The main problems were identified in administrative and bureaucratic issues, in economy, in social cohesion and inclusion, in housing and in mobility. With regard to the multi-dimensional policy recommendations and solutions matrix, the information about procedures for migrants should be improved at a local level, located in “safety and stability”. Nevertheless, this recommendation goes along with an improvement of the accessibility to services for mobility in rural regions at regional level, interconnected with mobility in rural development at this level. Alternatively, online access is recommended for the social connection, which needs to be implemented at national level. The complexity of the accessibility to services and information is highly inter-related in different areas of integration and needs to be handled at different governance levels. For further insights in the policy recommendations and solutions to meet the main challenges in the Spanish case study region refer to the multi-dimensional policy recommendation matrix below.

1. Government level: local

Areas of integration			
Economy & Employment	Housing	Education	Health
In general:	In general:	In general:	In general:
	Increase the capacity of municipalities to offer social housing - more autonomy to municipalities (S. Regional Level).	Increase the autonomy and investment for the Adult Education Centers (CPEPA) - "Certificates of Professionalism" (S. Regional Level).	No information added.
Labour migrants:	Labour migrants:	Labour migrants:	Labour migrants:
"Creation of Local Catalogues of Occupations with Difficult Coverage" to speed up the hiring of foreign people in relation to the needs of the labour market (s. Local level).			

Solutions:	Solutions:	Solutions:	Solutions:
Similar initiative is already being developed in a municipality on the urban outskirts of Madrid, where a local catalog of occupations -that are difficult to cover-is published, it is updated according to the demand of the labor market in the area (Participant, Regional roundtable).			

Areas of integration		
Social connection/cohesion	Language & culture	Safety & stability
In general:	In general:	In general:
Campaigns against racism and xenophobia: more visibility to the migratory phenomenon (s. National & Regional Level).	No information added.	Improve the information available to immigrants on how to carry out procedures and procedures - (s. Local Level).
Family migrants:	Family migrants:	Family migrants:
Reactivate the figure of the 'coexistence agents' and intercultural mediators (s. Regional level).		

Solutions:	Solutions:	Solutions:
<p>”Coexistence agents” (normally of foreign origin) hired by the Social Action sections of the regions who work for the reception, orientation and intercultural mediation with foreign seasonal workers for agricultural campaigns (Participant, Regional roundtable).</p>		<p>In some municipalities there is already a good practice of publishing books/guides/tutorials with information for migrants in municipalities (Participant third sector organization, discussion group CSWG Los Monegros + participant, Roundtable1, national level).</p>

Areas of integration		
Mobility	Rights & Citizenship	Rural/regional development
In general:	In general:	In general:
<p>Job recognition of the function performed by local administration staff (municipalities and counties) (s. Local Level).</p>	<p>Campaigns against racism and xenophobia: more visibility of the migratory phenomenon (Regional L). Reform of the local regime and administrative simplification for decision-making in local governments (National and Regional level).</p>	<p>No information added.</p>
Labour migrants:	Labour migrants:	Labour migrants:
	<p>Extend the possibility of voting in municipal elections (e.g. by increasing the list of countries with agreement) (s. National Level).</p>	

2. Government level: regional

Areas of integration			
Economy & Employment	Housing	Education	Health
In general:	In general:	In general:	In general:
Development of professional training in rural areas, with a diversity of studies and adapted to the demands of the main sectors of economic activity according to region. (s. Regional Level).	Provision of housing in adequate conditions of habitability in rural areas. (S. Regional Level).	Training in digital skills (s. Regional Level).	No information added.
Labour migrants:	Labour migrants:	Labour migrants:	Labour migrants:
	Reinforce the responsibility of employers in terms of accommodation for seasonal workers (s. National and Regional Level).		

Solutions:	Solutions:	Solutions:	Solutions:
	Housing census (bad conditions) plus economic aid to condition them and offer them social rent, it is working in some municipalities (Participant, Group discussion CSWG).	Courses through adult training centres (Participant, regional roundtable 2).	

Areas of integration		
Social connection/cohesion	Language & culture	Safety & stability
In general:	In general:	In general:
Social Connection: Improve accessibility to online services in rural and mountain areas (S. National and Regional Level) Social Cohesion: Reactivate the figure of cultural mediators in educational centres (s. Regional Level).	No information added.	No information added.
Solutions:	Solutions:	Solutions:
Connections: Continue and accelerate the process initiated by the government of Aragon from the Department of Science, University and Knowledge Society to be able to bring broadband to the municipalities in collaboration with the Provincial Councils (Participant, regional roundtable). Social Cohesion: Increase hiring and maintain these from the beginning of the school year (Participant, regional roundtable).		

Areas of integration		
Mobility	Rights & Citizenship	Rural/regional development
In general:	In general:	In general:
Improve accessibility to services in person in rural and mountain areas through the development of interurban transport. Plan for a New Road Transport Concession Map (s.. Regional Level).	Labour recognition of the function carried out from the municipalities (S. Regional Level).	Economy & Employment: Improve accessibility to online services in rural and mountain areas, and training in digital skills. To bring broadband to the municipalities (S. Regional Level).
Other:	Other:	Education:
		More technology training for these groups. To offer new/adapted studies on a rotating basis in the different population centres/towns (S. Regional Level). Many migrants come from densely urban contexts in their countries of origin, and they seem used to a lifestyle that has little to do with the mountain and rural ones.
Labour migrants:	Labour migrants:	Mobility:
		To organize integrated routes (buses for school transport but that can be used by the population (combined use). To densify the transport network (s.. Regional level).

3. Government level: national

Areas of integration			
Economy & Employment	Housing	Education	Health
In general:	In general:	In general:	In general:
<p>1. Streamline the administrative procedures for renewing residence and work permits (S. National Level).</p> <p>2. Decentralization of job catalogues with difficult coverage to increase hiring and meet the demands of the economic activity of the area. (S. National and Regional Level).</p> <p>3. Reforms the Migration Law so that immigrants can work in low-demand economic sectors (S. National level).</p>	<p>Challenges: not equal and adequate housing policies; low access to housing facilities.</p> <p>Possible solutions/recommendations: reverse the trend to structured policies to welcome TCNs.</p>	No information added.	No information added.
Labour migrants:	Labour migrants:	Labour migrants:	Labour migrants:
Avoid situations of supervening irregularity by not being able to obtain a new residence permit due to lack of an employment contract of a minimum duration of one year. (s. National Level).	Reinforce the responsibility of employers in terms of accommodation and to intensify inspection protocols since it is a responsibility of employers.		

<p>- Adapt the Immigration Law to the current Labour Reform and to eliminate those articles that position the foreign person in second place.</p> <p>Possible solutions/recommendations: better target work visa permission; widening micro-credit opportunities and access; guidance and mentorship programme; Improve public opinion and political actors' knowledge of the contribution of foreign immigrants to the Italian economy and society.</p>	<p>- Campaigns on the use and social responsibility of housing.</p> <p>- Campaigns to encourage renting without distinction of origin or ethnicity. (Regional and National level).</p>		
<p>Solutions:</p>	<p>Solutions:</p>	<p>Solutions:</p>	<p>Solutions:</p>
<p>Promote hiring at origin in some regions, like Andalusia (Huelva) (Participant, National Roundtable 1)</p> <p>-The Ministry of Inclusion, Social Security and Migration has launched a regulatory reform to give work permits to immigrants who occupy jobs that are not covered and who remain free. This will be done in three ways: 1) expanding hiring at origin (not only with temporary workers);</p> <p>2) allowing foreign students to work;</p> <p>3) allowing irregular immigrants to train in jobs where personnel are needed (Participant, Roundtable 1 National level).</p>	<p>The central government, from the General Secretariat for the Demographic Challenge, has developed measures applicable to the management of housing in rural areas, which will be implemented in collaboration with the governments of the autonomous communities.</p>		

Areas of integration		
Social connection/cohesion	Language & culture	Safety & stability
In general:	In general:	In general:
Social Connection: Improve accessibility to online services in rural and mountain areas (S. National and Regional Level).	No information added.	Request to have to stop passing an exam to access Spanish nationality (or reduce the difficulty) (S. National Level).
Labour migrants:	Labour migrants:	Labour migrants:
Improve online access through the portals of the Ministry, simplifying both in form and in language, (S. National Level).		
Family reunion:	Family reunion:	Family reunion:
		Increasing and bringing the immigration offices closer to the citizen in rural areas (S. National Level).
Solutions:	Solutions:	Solutions:
The General Directorate for the Demographic Challenge (Ministry for the Ecological Transition and the Demographic Challenge) has carried out a plan with 130 measures, among which it is contemplated to extend the network with a speed of 100 megabytes for the entire territory. (Participant, Regional roundtable 2).		

Areas of integration		
Mobility	Rights & Citizenship	Rural/regional development
In general:	In general:	In general:
No information added.	Application for Waiver of the exam to access Spanish nationality (S. National Level).	Increase multilevel management (S. National and Regional Level).
Solutions:	Solutions:	Solutions:
		Creation of Territorial Innovation Centers (Participant, national roundtable).

4. Government level: European

Areas of integration			
Economy & Employment	Housing	Education	Health
In general:	In general:	In general:	In general:
No information added.	No information added.	No information added.	No information added.

Areas of integration		
Social connection/cohesion	Language & culture	Safety & stability
In general:	In general:	In general:
No information added.	No information added.	Intensify and extend the presence of Frontex operations in the Canary archipelago and other European borders (s. National Level and European level)
Solutions:	Solutions:	Solutions:
		Currently, "Indalo" operation, which covers the Western Mediterranean and monitors all activities on the Western Mediterranean route between Morocco and Spain. border surveillance tasks, and rescue of immigrants [https://frontex.europa.eu/we-support/main-operations/operations-minerva-indalo-spain/ (accessed last: 06.06.2022)].

Areas of integration		
Mobility	Rights & Citizenship	Rural/regional development
In general:	In general:	In general:
No information added.		No information added.
Asylum seekers:	Asylum seekers:	Asylum seekers:
	Reform of the EU asylum system -Application procedures in the EU should also be harmonised. -The acceptance should also be proportional to the level of development of the countries, assuming that responsibility (National and European Level).	

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Sweden

Author: Zuzana Macuchova

The case study research in Dalarna, Sweden was conducted in the thematic frame of labour market integration and education. While the job opportunities and requested skills were specifically discussed with TCNs and local employers in Hedemora and Vansbro municipality, language learning and diversity in communication were emphasised with the public administration and stakeholders in the field of integration in Vansbro (Mathisen & Hansson 2022). Hence, the main elaborated policy problems are located in the areas of integration economy and employment, education as well as language. Accordingly, the unemployment of migrants is higher than of natives. Additionally, there is a gender gap among the migrants. These differences can be explained by the interrelation of language skills with work opportunities in Sweden. The policy recommendations of language training in combination with work, consequently, inter-relates with all the aforementioned areas of integration and needs to be considered at different governance levels (local and national). For further insights in the policy recommendations and solutions to meet the main challenges in the Swedish case study regions refer to the multi-dimensional policy recommendation matrix below.

1. Government level: local

Areas of integration			
Economy & Employment	Housing	Education	Health
In general:	In general:	In general:	In general:
<p>Dalarna (D): lack of knowledge on local employers, which would facilitate employment possibilities of asylum seekers.</p> <p>>Consolidate current knowledge about the labour market, about companies' need when it comes to hiring new employees.</p> <p>D: Lack of cooperation between local employers and education partners.</p> <p>>Offer arenas for networking between local companies and education partners.</p>	<p>No information added.</p>	<p>D: Women are less involved in introductory programs and language courses of Swedish for foreigners (SFI).</p> <p>>Investigate reasons behind differences between women's and men's involvement in SFI.</p> <p>D: Women are performing worse compared to men, i.e. takes longer time to finish</p> <p>>Investigate reasons behind differences between women's and men's performance in SFI.</p>	

Asylum seekers:	Asylum seekers:	Asylum seekers:	Asylum seekers:
			D: Currently, not so much focus on public health of asylum seekers >Strengthen the focus because it is fundamental to cohesion and a sustainable working life
Solutions:	Solutions:	Solutions:	Solutions:
D: Good results of combination of SFI course in connection with work/practice. >Continue with the combination of language courses with welding training or chef training.			

Areas of integration		
Social connection/cohesion	Language & culture	Safety & stability
In general:	In general:	In general:
D: Burden on civil society might be too heavy, risk to deteriorate it. >consolidate knowledge about which meeting places there exist in municipalities when it comes to integration work.	No information added.	No information added.
Refugees:	Refugees:	Refugees:
D: Burden on civil society might be too heavy, risk to deteriorate it. >consolidate knowledge about which meeting places there exist in municipalities when it comes to integration work.		

Areas of integration		
Mobility	Rights & Citizenship	Rural/regional development
In general:	In general:	In general:
No information added.	No information added.	No information added.

2. Government level: regional

Areas of integration			
Economy & Employment	Housing	Education	Health
In general:	In general:	In general:	In general:
<p>D: Lack of knowledge on local employers, which would facilitate employment possibilities</p> <p>>Decide what organ on a regional level will coordinate and establishing a platform for communication on integration in the region</p> <p>D: It might be difficult to commute to more remote parts of the region</p> <p>>Develop solutions for more efficient public transport in rural areas</p>	No information added.	No information added.	No information added.

Areas of integration		
Social connection/cohesion	Language & culture	Safety & stability
In general:	In general:	In general:
No information added.	No information added.	No information added.

Areas of integration		
Mobility	Rights & Citizenship	Rural/regional development
In general:	In general:	In general:
D: It might be difficult to commute to more remote parts of the region with public transport >A goal should be to foster stronger connections between rural and urban areas and to increase the mobility possibilities of the rural population in general and those without access to a car more specifically.	No information added.	No information added.

3. Government level: national

Areas of integration			
Economy & Employment	Housing	Education	Health
In general:	In general:	In general:	In general:
D: Knowledge on local labour market ouch local matching is difficult without physical employment offices. >Strive for physical meeting places, besides digital solutions.	No information added.	D: Language educations combined with employment are offered at a municipal level. >The opportunities for cooperation between municipalities need to be improved, which may require a change in the law. This would enable to join programs in neighbourhooding municipalities.	No information added.

Areas of integration		
Social connection/cohesion	Language & culture	Safety & stability
In general:	In general:	In general:
No information added.	No information added.	No information added.

Areas of integration		
Mobility	Rights & Citizenship	Rural/regional development
In general:	In general:	In general:
No information added.	No information added.	No information added.

4. Government level: European

Areas of integration			
Economy & Employment	Housing	Education	Health
In general:	In general:	In general:	In general:
No information added.	No information added.	No information added.	No information added.

Areas of integration		
Social connection/cohesion	Language & culture	Safety & stability
In general:	In general:	In general:
No information added.	No information added.	No information added.

Areas of integration		
Mobility	Rights & Citizenship	Rural/regional development
In general:	In general:	In general:
No information added.	No information added.	No information added.

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Turkey

Authors: Ayhan Kaya, Fatma Yilmaz-Elmas

In Turkey, the focus was on the rural peculiarities and the impact of immigration in the context of agricultural production in the rural case study region Karacabey. The agricultural industries and its synergies are of high advantage for the rural development in this region. Nevertheless, there is a shortage of labour force and in consequence, a high demand of foreign labour force (especially in the summer period), to continue a sustainable local development. With the attendance of migrant workers, mainly Syrians under Temporary Protection Status (TPS), different challenges arise (Kaya & Yilmaz-Elmas 2022), e.g. the residence permit status, the informality of labour, child labour and in consequence, dropouts in schools, temporariness and separation. Following, the multi-dimensional policy recommendations and solutions matrix mainly focuses on the areas of integration in this context. For example, the central recommendations for economy and employment at local level are to enable a rights-based approach and an equal and fair access to the labour market. This is overlapping with the national level, where the revision of the Labour Law is recommended. Both are interdependent with the recommendation for rural development at national level to offer support for agricultural, seasonal workers by trade unions. Such improvements at different governance levels might support the fight against informality. For further insights in the policy recommendations and solutions to meet the main challenges in the Turkish case study region refer to the multi-dimensional policy recommendation matrix below.

1. Government level: local

Areas of integration			
Economy & Employment	Housing	Education	Health
In general:	In general:	In general:	In general:
<p>Rights-based approach by all local actors in communicating with migrants.</p> <p>Ensuring equal & fair access to labour market procedures and the facilitation of full access to legal aid.</p>	<p>Ensuring better accommodation as most refugees are destitute and depend on temporarily hosts:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - develop programs of quality control to ensure minimum quality and safety standards in housing. <p>Sustainable Accommodation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - local municipal actors & the local representatives of the central state actors together with local employers make sure that migrants are granted the possibility to have a decent accommodation during their stay in the given locality - organise sustainable accommodation facilities for seasonal migrant workers with the support of local stakeholders and civil society organisations. 	<p>No information added.</p>	<p>No information added.</p>

Asylum seekers:	Asylum seekers:	Asylum seekers:	Asylum seekers:
	Problems in finding private accommodation due to language barriers, prejudices, lack of work permits, etc. - develop programs of quality control to ensure minimum quality and safety standards in housing.		

Areas of integration		
Social connection/cohesion	Language & culture	Safety & stability
In general:	In general:	In general:
Engaging the media: - implementation of a communication strategy to appeal to the local media promoting solidarity and human protection values, with biographies and refugee testimonials, and an explanation of how they relate to all of the native population by the local branch of Directorate Migration Management.	Engaging the media: - implementation of a communication strategy to appeal to the local media promoting solidarity and human protection values, with biographies and refugee testimonials, and an explanation of how they relate to all of the native population by the local branch of Directorate Migration Management.	No information added.

Areas of integration		
Mobility	Rights & Citizenship	Rural/regional development
In general:	In general:	In general:
No information added.	No information added.	<p>Agri-tourism and eco-tourism: financial opportunities to develop and pursue new projects in agro-tourism and eco-tourism for locals</p> <p>Organic agriculture: opportunity to learn the technics of organic agricultural production</p> <p>Cooperatives of local business associations & local municipalities with agricultural producers to organise the sale & transportation of products to outside markets.</p> <p>Smart Villages are established to be trained to develop skills about the use of technology & efficient methods in agricultural production, marketing, sale, communication.</p>
Solutions:	Solutions:	Solutions:
		Smart Village: implemented like in the city of Aydın (see http://www.vodafoneakillikoy.com/).

2. Government level: regional

Areas of integration			
Economy & Employment	Housing	Education	Health
In general:	In general:	In general:	In general:
No information added.	No information added.	No information added.	No information added.

Areas of integration		
Social connection/cohesion	Language & culture	Safety & stability
In general:	In general:	In general:
No information added.	No information added.	No information added.

Areas of integration		
Mobility	Rights & Citizenship	Rural/regional development
In general:	In general:	In general:
No information added.	No information added.	No information added.

3. Government level: national

Areas of integration			
Economy & Employment	Housing	Education	Health
In general:	In general:	In general:	In general:
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Preventing Child Labour: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - the Ministry of National Education collaborate with the relevant local actors, land owners; - Inform and train the producers about the negative consequences of child labour. - local actors and international institutions collaborate to offer educational and child-care services to the migrant communities. • Amendment of the Labour Law: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - revise the Labour Law No 4857 to better recognize the rights of migrant labour. 	<p>No information added.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Access to education: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - increase childcare access and language course opportunities and incentives so that adults are better able to attend language courses. • Preventing drop-outs in schools: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - measures to change the conditions that weaken migrant children's ties with school after their enrolment in the education system should be planned and implemented in order to prevent the school dropouts: - train teachers to be informed about intercultural communication; - strengthen the Turkish language training for the Syrian students; 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Access to health services: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - consider the need of refugees and migrants who suffer from health problems, including emotional or mental disorders that require prompt professional treatment. - make Arabic translators available at all hospitals and government offices, and hospital staff should be trained regarding migrant needs.

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - engage students' parents through their children to become more integrated to the schooling activities; - better inform the local students about the difficulties that the Syrians face in everyday life so that Syrian children will not be often exposed to peer pressure. 	
Refugees:	Refugees:	Refugees:	Refugees:
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improving employment opportunities: It is widely accepted that dependence on the state is reduced when refugees are working. Refugees should, preferably, be granted permission to work so that they could generate an independent financial self-sufficiency to maintain an adequate standard of living. The state should simplify and standardize the process of ensuring recognition of qualifications and university degrees earned in the countries of origin. 			

Areas of integration		
Social connection/cohesion	Language & culture	Safety & stability
In general:	In general:	In general:
	No information added.	No information added.
Refugees:	Refugees:	Refugees:
Local municipalities organise get-together meetings for immigrants and the native populations in different neighbourhoods where there is a critical mass of migrants.		
Labour migrants:	Labour migrants:	Labour migrants:
Local municipalities organise get-together meetings for immigrants and the native populations in different neighbourhoods where there is a critical mass of migrants.		

Areas of integration		
Mobility	Rights & Citizenship	Rural/regional development
In general:	In general:	In general:
No information added.	No information added.	In general: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Revision of the Law 6360: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - revise the Law No. 6360, according to which the legal entity of villages was removed in the provinces in order to prompt the inhabitants of villages to invest in agricultural production.

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Long-term perspective for rural sustainable development: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - work in collaboration with all relevant state actors, local municipal actors, scientists, and civil society organisations to develop a more holistic and sustainable rural and agricultural development goals. Economy & Employment: • Labour Unions: - be more engaged in supporting and organising agricultural and seasonal workers. • Improving the image of agricultural workers and rural jobs: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - strengthen the image of businesses related to farming and agricultural production. • Amendment of the Greater Municipality Law (Law No 5216): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -revise the Law on Greater Municipalities in order to make the villages to regain their village status. • Amendment of the Law on Protection of Agricultural Lands (Law No 5403): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -revise the Law on Protection of Agricultural Lands to make sure that inheritance of agricultural lands can be peacefully resolved among the members of the family without having the time pressure.
Other:	Other:	Other:
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Climate change and migration: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - consider climate change with its different aspects as a part of even short-term planning. - include climate change in any national level sustainable development plan on migration due to its consequences on rural migration, rural poverty and food insecurity.

4. Government level: European

Areas of integration			
Economy & Employment	Housing	Education	Health
In general:	In general:	In general:	In general:
No information added.	No information added.	No information added.	No information added.

Areas of integration		
Social connection/cohesion	Language & culture	Safety & stability
In general:	In general:	In general:
No information added.	No information added.	No information added.

Areas of integration		
Mobility	Rights & Citizenship	Rural/regional development
In general:	In general:	In general:
No information added.	No information added.	No information added.

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United Kingdom (Scotland)

Authors: Michele Bianchi, Maria Luisa Caputo

The case study region in Scotland was the Outer Hebrides, which is a group of islands on the western edges of Scotland. The thematic focus was the impact of a small share of migrants within the total population on the long-term sustainability of the local community and economy, with special emphasis on the fishing sector facing a labour shortage (Caputo et. al. 2022). The main problems in this region are the depopulation (emigration of young people, immigration of British pensioners), the challenging mobility (on/across the islands and from/to the mainland), lack of affordable housing, and since Brexit workforce scarcity threatening the survival of the fishing industry in this region. Migration – on the other hand – contributes to the population balance and to the local economy. However, migration is restricted by the post-Brexit migration system, which did not create a route for the “unskilled” workers, previously filled by EU migrants from countries part of the 2004 EU enlargement.

The UK’s migration policy does not respond to the needs of the local communities and economy. Sponsorship and skilled work visa to the UK are inadequate as they are expensive (the administrative process, the fees, and the salary threshold) and in the analysed case study always unsuccessful because the migrant did not meet the English language requirement. Recommendations to lower these barriers and to approach English as a goal and a mean for integration are mentioned at British level in the integration area “language and culture” in the matrix. Above all, this migration policy negatively affects the rural development. Furthermore, it is recommended at Scottish national level to facilitate the settlement of migrants in rural and remote regions. As an example of good practice, the matrix refers to the resettlement scheme for refugees in rural and remote Scottish regions. For further insights in the policy recommendations and solutions to meet the main challenges in the Scottish case study regions refer to the multi-dimensional policy recommendation matrix below.

1. Government level: local

Areas of integration			
Economy & Employment	Housing	Education	Health
In general:	In general:	In general:	In general:
<p>Problems (P): Difficulties for local firms to find workforce.</p> <p>Recommendations (R): To design a local system that offers a job position linked with integration opportunities.</p>	<p>P: Housing scarcity and unaffordable prices on the private market.</p> <p>R: To dis-incentive locals to rent properties for short-term vacation and put the asset on long-term rental.</p> <p>P: The social housings are few, mostly in Stornoway, and far away from many fishing industries that most need new workers.</p> <p>R: To coordinate the social housing planning with requests from the economic sectors.</p>		<p>P: Challenges in accessing health services, notably in the most remote areas and for specialised health issues. The health system is increasingly oriented toward an ageing population, and therefore essential services e.g. Maternity wards are not provided anymore elsewhere then in the Stornoway Hospital.</p> <p>R: To design a health system of proximity for remote communities.</p>
Labour migrants:	Labour migrants:	Labour migrants:	Labour migrants:
	P: Temporary accommodation might not be adequate.		

	R: To support local firms in finding accommodations with better conditions and to facilitate the building of new venues.		
Family migrants:	Family migrants:	Family migrants:	Family migrants:
P: To find job for both partners. R: In the local scheme for job offers, these have to be associated with other potential jobs for partners.	P: housing is a barrier for migrant family to settle (difficulty to bring over the family without a proper accommodation). Social housing partially responded to their needs but there are few available options and not always in the same islands/area where firms are located. R: To create a scheme to offer a combination of job positions and adequate accommodations in remote communities.		

Solutions:	Solutions:	Solutions:	Solutions:
Refugees are well supported in their integration in the local labour market – both in terms of acquisition of competences to use locally, and of support to become self-employed and open their own business.	The Hebridean Housing Partnership and the Local Council already discuss the investment plan. They can extend the dialogue to local economic actors.	Migrants and refugees attend higher education in the islands thanks to the presence of a college. A Local third sector organizations works to match professional education and job market gaps.	Social workers accompany the refugees to register in the local GP practice and therefore to access health cares.

Areas of integration		
Social connection/cohesion	Language & culture	Safety & stability
In general:	In general:	In general:
P: In remote communities, social connections might be few. R: To incentivate access to the volunteering sectors as an occasion of encounter between migrants and locals.	P: ESOL classes are currently limited to refugees. R: To expand these to migrants who need them.	

Labour migrants:	Labour migrants:	Labour migrants:
	P: ESOL not provided for them. R: To provide more ESOL classes also in partnership with firms to optimize migrants' time.	P: Migration status and living conditions potentially put at risk of exploitations migrant workers in the Western Isles. R: To assist them and firms to find adequate conditions for temporary permanence.
Family migrants:	Family migrants:	Family migrants:
	P: Migrant families rarely choose classes for Gaelic education. R: To incentive the learning of Gaelic through new initiatives.	
Solutions:	Solutions:	Solutions:
Befriend initiatives are in place. Locals are in touch with Syrian and Afghani refugees and they go out once per week to have a coffee, discover the territory, have a chat, get information about something. The volunteers run childcares to allow refugees to participate in English classes.	Provision of quasi-individualised ESOL classes linked to childcares facilities for refugees.	

Areas of integration		
Mobility	Rights & Citizenship	Rural/regional development
In general:	In general:	In general:
<p>P: Mobility can be difficult without a private vehicle. R: To provide migrants with resources to pay driving lessons.</p> <p>P: Links between islands and the mainland are challenging due to an ageing ferry fleet. R: To advocate toward the local transport authority the request for adequate connections.</p> <p>P: Flights to the mainland are expensive. R: To facilitate travels to the home country with an island allowance.</p>	<p>P: Important changes in the right of EU migrants living in the Western Isles since Brexit. People willing to migrate in the Western Isles under the Skilled Worker Visa were unable to do so because of the English skills (B1) requirement. R: No solution at local level. See the regional and national scale.</p>	<p>Depopulation strongly affects the rural development of the Outer Hebrides. Migration can contribute to the survival of these communities and their economic sectors.</p>

		Economy & Employment:
		Job offer have to encompass also accommodation, access to local service, and other job offers for partners.
		Housing:
		Costs on private market are high; most of the available houses are for short-term rental for tourism. R: Collaborations with local economic actors.
		Education:
		Range of opportunities for migrants to enter education and training and better their job position, starting new enterprises and participating in the economic development of the region.
		Health:
		The challenges in accessing health cares and the cares oriented increasively toward an ageing population are a barrier to regional development. R: To design a health system of proximity for all the population and facilitated ways to access it for migrants.
		Social connection/cohesion:
		Social cohesion in those small, rural communities is strong and it is an asset for rural development. R: To incentive voluntary sector as a way to connect migrants and communities.

		Language & culture:
		English skills among migrants is an important indicator of their social inclusion. Migrants with Gaelic skills generally contribute to the continuation and to the valorisation of the local language and culture. R: Further opportunities for migrants to access resources to learn English.
		Safety & stability:
		Rural development cannot be based on economic activities who put migrant workers at risk of exploitation. R: Attention need to be given to migrants in labour intensive sectors.
Labour migrants:	Labour migrants:	Labour migrants:
	P: Difficulties in access EU settlement and pre-settlement Status or Frontier worker visa to guarantee some of their previous rights, as they did not have all the needed proof (e.g. in the case of informal accommodation or self-employed position).	The current migration system makes the arrival and settlement difficult for them. These challenges broke the migration chains that worked in the previous 15-20years that brought people to the Western Isles. R: See the regional and national scale for details on the review of migration policy.

	R: No solution at local level. See the regional and national scale.	
		Mobility:
		Mobility from/to the islands is also highly challenging. R: To develop further the mobility system to this area.
Solutions:	Solutions:	Solutions:
	Scottish Rural Visa Pilot.	To take inspiration from the resettlement schemes for Asylum Seekers and Refugees to design a local-based plan for integration and settlement

2. Government level: regional

Areas of integration			
Economy & Employment	Housing	Education	Health
In general:	In general:	In general:	In general:
<p>P: Scotland looks for migrant workers in many sectors of its economy and with specific needs of workforce established at local level.</p> <p>R: To advocate for a revision of the national migration policy.</p>	<p>P: In remote areas second homes, tourism oriented rental market and housing stock in bad conditions highly limit the availability of housing.</p> <p>R: To incentive the rental of properties into local scheme for migrants' settlement.</p>		<p>P: Rural and remote areas strongly rely on the health services provided in the urban areas. They travel there to access specialised cares.</p> <p>R: To provide adequate support to arrive at the health services from the remote areas.</p>
Refugees:	Refugees:	Refugees:	Refugees:
<p>P: They face challenges in entering the labour market.</p> <p>R: To work with private sector and third sector to develop initiatives to facilitate their entrance.</p>		<p>P: Refugees' skills are often not recognised and they require to do new training.</p> <p>R: To recognize adequately these backgrounds and facilitate refugees' access to</p>	

<p>P: Their skills are often not recognised and they require to do new training. R: To support them with dedicated training and professional education in accordance to their background.</p>		<p>program to recognize officially their skills.</p>	
<p>Labour migrants:</p>	<p>Labour migrants:</p>	<p>Labour migrants:</p>	<p>Labour migrants:</p>
<p>P: Shortage of migrant workers in different sectors. R: Rural visa scheme with detailed list of shortage for each region.</p>	<p>Accommodation was also proven to challenge their access to their rights (as in the case of accessing the settlement status).</p> <p>P: Temporary accommodation might not be adequate and put them at risk of exploitation as in the case of the fishing and tourism industry when migrants live in their workplace. R: To integrate the job offers in rural areas with accommodations.</p>		

Solutions:	Solutions:	Solutions:	Solutions:
To create a migration system that takes into account the lack of workforce in rural Scotland as proposed by the Rural Visa Scheme pilot of the Expert Advisory Group on Migration of the Scottish Government and supported by the Migration Advisory Committee of the British government.	To create a migration system that takes into account the scarcity of accommodation in rural Scotland as proposed by the Rural Visa Scheme pilot of the Expert Advisory Group on Migration of the Scottish Government and supported by the Migration Advisory Committee of the British government.		Refugees have the right to NHS healthcare. Social worker accompany the refugees to register in the local GP practice and therefore to access health cares.

Areas of integration		
Social connection/cohesion	Language & culture	Safety & stability
In general:	In general:	In general:
No information added.	P: Reduction of the ESOL provision, in some Local Authorities they are active only for refugees. R: To integrate further this offer also for other migrants who need it.	No information added.
Refugees:	Refugees:	Refugees:
	P: Refugees of the Syrian Vulnerable People Resettlement Program found hard to study English in a formal way and to wait to access the labour market once they attain a certain level of English.	

	R: To integrate this with internship in local firms.	
Solutions:	Solutions:	Solutions:
	ESOL classes for refugees.	

Areas of integration		
Mobility	Rights & Citizenship	Rural/regional development
In general:	In general:	In general:
<p>P: Difficulties to connect rural and remote areas.</p> <p>P: The flight links are generally too expensive to be afforded by labour migrants.</p> <p>R: To consider incentive for supporting the moving costs for those who want to move and settle in a rural remote area in the form of an Island allowance.</p>	<p>P: The current migration system cannot meet the need of newcomers for rural Scottish regions that face depopulation and lack of workforce</p> <p>R: To implement a migration system that can facilitate the settlement of migrant population in rural and remote Scottish regions as proposed by the Rural Visa Scheme pilot of the Expert Advisory Group on Migration of the Scottish Government and supported by the Migration Advisory Committee of the British government.</p>	<p>In many rural areas, the absence of newcomers is compromising the survival of many firms.</p> <p>R: To implement a migration system that can facilitate the settlement of migrant population in rural and remote Scottish regions as proposed by the Rural Visa Scheme pilot. This would be by providing a route for migrants willing to fulfill positions who are in labour shortage or in sectors who are considered key for the local development.</p>
Solutions:	Solutions:	Solutions:
The Scottish Government has already implemented a form of Highlands and Isles allowance but it can be improved.		

3. Government level: national

Areas of integration			
Economy & Employment	Housing	Education	Health
In general:	In general:	In general:	In general:
<p>P: The UK Gov is the main policy-maker. There is disagreement between the Scottish and UK government on the migration policy. The current migration system does not consider the necessities of rural areas.</p> <p>R: To pressure for a revision of the Tier-point system and introduction of regional-based shortage list.</p>	No information added.	No information added.	No information added.
Solutions:	Solutions:	Solutions:	Solutions:
The Scottish government proposes a Shortage Occupation List on the basis of regional needs.			

Areas of integration		
Social connection/cohesion	Language & culture	Safety & stability
In general:	In general:	In general:
No information added.	<p>P: The requirement of B1 in English that the Tier-point system requests for newcomers is a barrier for many migrant workers.</p> <p>R: To ask for a facilitation on the requirement for migrants who agree to work in remote areas.</p>	No information added.

Areas of integration		
Mobility	Rights & Citizenship	Rural/regional development
In general:	In general:	In general:
No information added.	<p>P: Many foreign workers do not consider to move to the UK rural areas because of the complexity to obtain a working visa under the new conditions of the migration policy.</p> <p>R: To implement a policy framework dedicated to the migration to rural areas intertwined with the solutions described in the lower levels</p>	
Solutions:	Solutions:	Solutions:
	To allow the Rural Visa Scheme Pilot for Scotland.	To allow the Rural Visa Scheme Pilot for Scotland.

4. Government level: European

Areas of integration			
Economy & Employment	Housing	Education	Health
In general:	In general:	In general:	In general:
No information added.	No information added.	No information added.	No information added.

Areas of integration		
Social connection/cohesion	Language & culture	Safety & stability
In general:	In general:	In general:
No information added.	No information added.	No information added.

Areas of integration		
Mobility	Rights & Citizenship	Rural/regional development
In general:	In general:	In general:
No information added.	No information added.	After Brexit, the UK is independent from the EU policy and decisions; therefore, it is not possible to examine problems and recommendations.

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Conclusion

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The policy recommendations and solution matrix of each MATILDE country aimed to highlight the most relevant policy issues and their interconnectedness. The case studies had a thematic as well as a governance focus that was elaborated and validated, targeting the related areas of integration, levels of governance, migrant groups and their interdependencies.

As the matrixes have shown, policies in migration and integration are strongly interconnected in different areas of integration (vertical) and at all government levels (horizontal), which is in line with the mid-level theory of Ager and Strang (2008), and affect groups of migrants differently (vertical). Nevertheless, political targets and objectives often differ or even contradict each other. For example, a decision at national level can impact the regional and local level negatively. The Brexit of the United Kingdom, e.g. led to a lack of EU-workforce that threatens the fishing industry in Scotland. Additionally, such decisions can result in conflicts in the implementation of the policies. For example, many MATILDE regions are struggling with labour shortages, but national restrictions for labour market integration of asylum seekers hinder to counteract this negative trend. Consequently, the matrixes with their inter-relations clearly demonstrate that

- the multi-level governance approach should be aimed for migration and integration policies, in order to achieve a coherent distribution of competencies and responsibilities of all involved policy actors, stakeholders and NGOs at all governance levels;
- the determination of competencies and responsibilities needs to be cleared;

- implementation of migration and integration policies should be evaluated, in order to avoid conflicts at the different government levels (horizontal) and among the different actors and/or departments (vertical);
- upcoming political decisions and legal frameworks should be evaluated beforehand (assessment of political and legal consequences), in order to avoid conflicts at the different government levels (horizontal) and among the different actors and/or departments (vertical);
- place-based policies are of importance for the rural development, in order to meet the needs of the rural and mountainous regions and of the population with and without a migrant background (bottom-up processes);

The policy recommendations and solution matrix has also shown coinciding needs between different countries addressed to the EU level. For example, Germany, Austria and Finland recommends to decrease the bureaucracy and complexity for applying for funding, in order to increase the access for NGOs and smaller municipalities or regions. Such simplifications would have a positive impact, when funding is gained, where it is needed. Furthermore, a reform of the EU's asylum system is requested, e.g. with standards for the asylum procedure and minimum standards for the accommodation and care, as the case study results of Austria and Spain show. In addition, this would help to clarify the responsibilities and competences in asylum issues.

To sum up, the interdependences of government levels (horizontal), areas of integration (vertical) and groups of migrants (diagonal) and especially the complexity of these interdependences evidence the importance of standards at highest level (EU), but place-based approaches at regional and local levels. A clarified distribution of competencies and responsibilities between the different actors and goals aiming at uniformly coordinated goals would increase the ability of immigration being a chance for rural development.